

University of Utrecht

ARTICLE 346 TFEU

A COMPARATIVE LEGAL ANALYSIS OF THE APPLICATION OF ARTICLE 346
TFEU IN PUBLIC PROCUREMENT IN THE DEFENCE SECTOR AND IMPLICATIONS
FOR EUROPEAN STRATEGIC AUTONOMY

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ABBREVIATIONS

1958 Arms List	Council Decision 255/58 of 15 April 1958 defining the list of arms, munitions, and war material referred to in Article 346(1)(b) TFEU
Article 346	Article 346 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union
Council	Council of the European Union
Court	Court of Justice of the European Union
CSDP	Common Security and Defence Policy
Directive	Directive 2009/81/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 July 2009 on the coordination of procedures for the award of certain works contracts, supply contracts and service contracts by contracting authorities or entities in the fields of defence and security [2009] OJ L216/76
EDTIB	European Defence Technological and Industrial Base
EU	European Union
GDTIB	German Defence Technological and Industrial Base
GWB	Gesetz gegen Wettbewerbsbeschränkungen
Minister	Minister of Defence
Ministry	Ministry of Defence
NATO	North Atlantic Treaty Organization
NLDTIB	Dutch Defence Technological and Industrial Base
TED	Tenders Electronic Daily
TEU	Treaty on the European Union
TFEU	Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union
US	United States
VWEU	Verdrag betreffende de werking van de Europese Unie

CHAPTER 1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. BACKGROUND AND RELEVANCE

Since the establishment of the European internal market, Article 346 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU) has allowed Member States to derogate from EU (European Union) law in matters that involve essential security interests.¹ Although this provision can apply broadly, its application is especially pronounced in the field of defence procurement, for which Article 346 allows a full exclusion from EU law when essential security interests are involved.² Prior to the adoption of the Defence Procurement Directive 2009/81/EC (Directive),³ defence procurement was already formally within the scope of EU procurement law.⁴ However, the absence of procurement regulation tailored to the specific needs of the defence sector made Article 346 a practical and commonly used tool for Member States to exclude procurements from EU law.

The application of Article 346 TFEU, though legally available, can lead to economic and industrial inefficiencies as well as fragmentation. Because Article 346 allows Member States to unilaterally remove defence procurement from the scope of harmonized EU rules, states can make procurement decisions in an uncoordinated manner, and resort to non-transparent, discriminatory, and protectionist procurement procedures. This is widely considered to undermine the capacity of European defence in two main ways. First, Article 346 leads to economic inefficiencies because the creation of a competitive and integrated European Defence Technological and Industrial Base (EDTIB) is hindered by discriminatory and protectionist procurement policies of the Member States of the EU, which favor military equipment produced by their own industries over that of other industries.⁵ Second, because of the resulting procurement decisions, the number of incompatible military systems and equipment undermines possibilities for cooperation and interoperability among European armed forces.⁶ In practice, these effects result in a duplication of military capabilities and missed opportunities for economies of scale. There is growing concern recently among different authorities that the fragmented market is not competitive enough and harms European defensive capabilities and competition,⁷ and two EU Parliament resolutions were passed

¹ Treaty establishing the European Economic Community, 1957, art 223; Treaty on European Union [1992] OJ C 191/1, art 296; Consolidated version of the Treaty establishing the European Community [2008] OJ C 115/47, art 296; Consolidated version of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union [2012] OJ C 326/47, art 346.

² Nathan Meershoek, 'Sovereignty and Interdependence in EU Military Procurement Regulation' (dissertation, Utrecht University 2023), pp 1-4.

³ Directive 2009/81/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 July 2009 on the coordination of procedures for the award of certain works contracts, supply contracts and service contracts by contracting authorities or entities in the fields of defence and security [2009] OJ L216/76 (Directive 2009/81/EC).

⁴ See, for example: Case C-414/97 *Commission of the European Communities v Kingdom of Spain* [1999] ECR I-5585.

⁵ Isabelle Loannides, *EU Defence Package: Defence Procurement and Intra-Community Transfer Directives: European Implementation Assessment* (Ex-Post Evaluation Unit 2020); Meershoek 2023 (3) (n 2), pp 2-5.

⁶ *ibid.*

⁷ Mario Draghi and others, *The future of European competitiveness: In-depth analysis and recommendations, Part B* (European Commission, 2024), pp 159-171; Sauli Niinistö, 'Safer Together: Strengthening Europe's Civilian and Military Preparedness and Readiness' (European Commission, 2024), pp 119-124; European Commission and High Representative of the Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy, 'White Paper for European Defence: Readiness 2030' (European Commission, 2025) <https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/e6d5db69-e0ab-4bec-9dc0-3867b4373019_en?filename=White+paper+for+European+defence+%E2%80%93+Readiness+2030.pdf> accessed 27 June 2025; Monopolies Commission, 'Statement: Why Competition Matters for Defence Spending' (2025) <https://www.monopolienkommission.de/images/PDF/Presse/Full%20Statement_Monopolien%20Commission.pdf> accessed 27 June 2025.

on this topic.⁸ It is true that Article 346 TFEU can also be invoked to facilitate military cooperation. That said, the existing legal instruments already provide room for cooperation, and it appears from my research that this ground for the invocation of Article 346 is insignificant.⁹

The two preceding reasons led to the Directive, which aims to harmonize procurement procedures across Member States and reduce reliance on Article 346 TFEU. The Directive functions within the framework of the internal market, and allows for proportionate security measures in defence procurement, while also ensuring transparency and non-discrimination where possible.¹⁰ By providing a legal framework specific to defence and introducing competition where possible, it sought to foster a more competitive EDTIB.¹¹

Despite the Directive's objectives, its impact on curbing the use of Article 346 TFEU has been limited. In practice, the Directive has had limited success¹²: on average, only 11.7% of defence spending was tendered competitively under the Directive through public procurements between 2016 and 2018.¹³ For the Netherlands, however, this was a negligible 0.8%, and for Germany just 1.8%.¹⁴

A broader indicator of the application of the Directive is the number of contract award notices published on the Tenders Electronic Daily (TED) platform. A contract award notice is the public summary of each defence contract awarded under the Directive, and under Article 30(3) of the Directive, the award notice must be submitted to TED no later than 48 days after the contract award. Between August 2011 and December 2014, the Netherlands published only 31 contract award notices on TED, while Germany published 550 contract award notices.¹⁵ Between 2016 and 2020, the Netherlands published 274 contract award notices, while Germany published 3106.¹⁶ Although the German numbers appear substantial, the total value of the German award notices between 2011 and 2014 amounted to only EUR 0.9 billion in spending.¹⁷ Moreover, in approximately 60% of these cases, the negotiated procedure without prior publication was used.¹⁸ As a result, the actual value of competitively tendered military contracts in Germany remains very low and under 2.0% of total defence procurement spending.

Therefore, large defence contracts continue to be awarded outside the scope of the Directive, with Article 346 TFEU serving as the legal basis for exclusion from standard procurement rules to make direct awards and require offsets in defence contracts in order to support national industries.¹⁹ Moreover, the application of Article 346 is not uniform. National practices

⁸ European Parliament, 'Implementation of the Common Security and Defence Policy: Annual Report 2024' (Resolution A-10-0011/2025, 2025) <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/TA-10-2025-0058_EN.html> accessed 27 June 2025, paras 47, 49; European Parliament, 'White paper on the future of European defence' (Resolution P10_TA(2025)0034, 2025) <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/TA-10-2025-0034_EN.html> accessed 27 June 2025, para 71.

⁹ No such invocations have been identified, as can be examined in Annex I and II.

¹⁰ Nathan Meershoek, 'Why the EU Internal market is Not the Correct Legal Basis for Regulating Military-strategic procurement: On Functional Division of Competences' (2022) 19 *European Law Review* 353.

¹¹ Directive 2009/81/EC, recitals 2, 3, 34, 55.

¹² The last comprehensive research about this data stems from 2020: Loannides 2020 (n 5), pp 86–98.

¹³ *ibid*, p 92.

¹⁴ *ibid*, p 93.

¹⁵ Hlne Masson and Kvin Martin, *The Directive 2009/81/EC on Defence and Security Procurement under Scrutiny* (Recherches & Documents No 03/2015, Fondation pour la Recherche Stratgique 2015) <<https://www.frstrategie.org/sites/default/files/documents/publications/recherches-et-documents/2015/201503.pdf?>> accessed 27 June 2025, p 20.

¹⁶ Loannides 2020 (n 5), pp 89-90.

¹⁷ Masson & Martin 2025 (n 15), pp 24-25.

¹⁸ *ibid*, pp 28-29.

¹⁹ Baudouin Heuninckx, '346, the Number of the Beast? A Blueprint for the Protection of Essential Security interests in EU Defence Procurement' (2018) 27 *PPLR* 51, 54; Meershoek 2023 (3) (n 2), pp 70-75, 83-89; Nathan Meershoek,

vary considerably regarding the integration of Article 346 into the national legal framework, the reasons for invocation, and the necessity and proportionality requirements for invocation. States retain full freedom whether or not to transpose Article 346 into their national legal systems, and states have broad discretion under Article 4(2) of the Treaty on the European Union (TEU) to determine their essential security interests. However, states cannot deviate from what accounts for a necessary and proportional invocation and utilization of the rights reserved under Article 346.²⁰ Nevertheless, especially since the start of the Russian invasion of Ukraine, Article 346 appears to be utilized to a higher extent, and the number of invocations also differs between countries.²¹ This increase and divergence in invocations raise concerns regarding the EU principle of uniform application of EU law. A fragmented approach to Article 346 allows for divergent interpretations of Article 346,²² which harms legal certainty, a general principle in EU law.²³

It cannot go unmentioned that the Western international security environment has undergone its most significant transformation since the end of the Cold War. The return of military threats on the European continent, in particular following Russia's invasion of Ukraine in 2022, has reignited calls for the EU to strengthen its role as a geopolitical actor.²⁴ The concept of European strategic autonomy, as coined by the 2016 Security Strategy of the EU,²⁵ and later reiterated by French President Macron,²⁶ increasingly has been framed as an objective in EU policy. Inherent in strategic autonomy is the capacity to act independently when necessary. However, the persistent reliance on Article 346 TFEU threatens to undermine European autonomy by reinforcing national fragmentation and impeding the emergence of an EDTIB.

1.2. RESEARCH PROBLEM AND AIM

In the context of the aforescribed background, Article 346 TFEU is a double-edged sword: it safeguards national sovereignty and essential security interests but simultaneously hampers efforts to create a unified and efficient defence procurement regime. As such, it lies at the heart of the constitutional structure of the EU today. The evolving tension between these principles necessitates an assessment of the application of Article 346, both from a legal and practical perspective. While the application and implementation of the Directive have been studied to some extent in previous research,²⁷ comparative studies on national codification and application in practice of Article 346

'Reciprocity as Security: Reconsidering Third Country Access to European Critical Infrastructure Procurement' (2023) 28 *European Foreign Affairs Review* 75, p. 87.

²⁰ See Chapter 2 for an overview of the legal framework of Article 346 TFEU.

²¹ KPMG, 'SWOT-analyse strategische waardeketens' (2020) <<https://www.tweedekamer.nl/kamerstukken/detail?id=2020D43347&did=2020D43347>> accessed 27 June 2025; Bundestag, 'Antwort der Bundesregierung auf die Kleine Anfrage der Fraktion der CDU/CSU: Zur Zukunft der deutschen Rüstungs- und Verteidigungsfähigkeit' (Drucksache 20/11868, 10 June 2024) <<https://dserver.bundestag.de/btd/20/118/2011868.pdf>> accessed 27 June 2025.

²² This will be further discussed in Chapter 5.

²³ Jérémie van Meerbeeck, 'The Principle of Legal Certainty in the Case Law of the European Court of Justice: From Certainty to Trust' (2016) 41 *European Law Review* 275.

²⁴ For example: European External Action Service, 'A Strategic Compass for Security and Defence: For a European Union that protects its citizens, values and interests and contributes to international peace and security' (2022) <https://www.eeas.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/strategic_compass_en3_web.pdf> accessed 27 June 2025.

²⁵ European External Action Service, 'Shared Vision, Common Action: A Stronger Europe: A Global Strategy for the European Union's Foreign and Security Policy' (2016) <https://www.eeas.europa.eu/sites/default/files/eugs_review_web_0.pdf> accessed 27 June 2025, pp 4, 9, 19, 45, 46; see also: Directive 2009/81/EC, recital 8.

²⁶ President Macron reiterated the idea in his *Sorbonne Speech*, see: Emmanuel Macron, 'Discours d'Emmanuel Macron pour une Europe souveraine, unie, démocratique' (Sorbonne Speech, Paris, 26 September 2017).

²⁷ European Commission, 'Report from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council on the implementation of Directive 2009/81/EC on public procurement in the fields of defence and security' COM(2016) 762 final; Loannides 2020 (n 5).

by Member States and the motivation thereof have not been conducted before. This highlights a research gap. Research on how Article 346 is applied is worthwhile, given the consequential nature of the Article. Understanding better how and why Article 346 is invoked can result in a better understanding of how and whether the current legal architecture can support the EU's strategic ambitions, or whether some form of legal or political reform would be needed.

In this comparative analysis, the Netherlands and Germany are selected for their contrasts. The Netherlands is selected because it has a small defence industry that is specialized in some niche areas.²⁸ Moreover, the Netherlands conducts its defence procurement processes relatively transparently.²⁹ Germany is chosen due to its substantial defence industry with almost 250 firms,³⁰ and the second highest defence spending in the EU. This provides a contrasting case to examine the application of Article 346 TFEU.

The aim of this study is threefold. First, academically, it offers a comparative legal analysis of how Article 346 TFEU is interpreted and applied in two EU Member States. Attention is paid to both the formal legal interpretation and the practical application of Article 346. This is not only academically important, but also practically. The Dutch government admitted that it does not know how other European countries exactly apply Article 346.³¹ By addressing this gap in knowledge in the government, this research should clarify the differences and similarities. Second, the study seeks to normatively evaluate whether the invocations should be considered as legal and align with the requirements set by the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU). Thirdly, actionable advice is offered to governments to enhance EU strategic autonomy.

1.3. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This thesis seeks to answer the following main research question:

How do the different national approaches of the Netherlands and Germany to the application of Article 346 TFEU in defence procurement align with the legal conditions established under EU law, and how could potential negative effects on EU strategic autonomy be mitigated?

To structurally answer the main research question, the following sub-questions are addressed in this research:

1. *What judicial principles and conditions of invocation have been established for Article 346 TFEU?*
2. *How does the Netherlands apply Article 346 TFEU in law and practice within its defence procurement policy?*

²⁸ Ministry of Defence and the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy, 'Defence Industry Strategy' (2018) <<https://www.defensie.nl/binaries/defensie/documenten/beleidsnota-s/2018/11/15/defensie-industrie-strategie/Defence%2BIndustry%2BStrategy.pdf>> accessed 27 June 2025.

²⁹ Large tenders are publicly discussed in parliament, see Annex I; moreover, see: Assemblée nationale, 'Mission « Flash » sur les marchés publics européens de défense' (2021) <https://www2.assemblee-nationale.fr/static/15/commissions/Defense/Communication-miflash_marches_publics_europeens.pdf> accessed 27 June 2025, p 31.

³⁰ Giampiero Giacomello and Oltion Preka 'Sources of strength: mapping the defence sector in Europe' (2023) 23 Defence Studies 531, pp 530-540; European Defence Agency, *Defence Data 2023–2024* (European Defence Agency 2024).

³¹ *Kamerstukken II 2021-2022*, 31516, nr. 36, p 9.

3. *How does Germany apply Article 346 TFEU in law and practice within its defence procurement policy?*
4. *How do the different approaches to the application of Article 346 TFEU align with the legal conditions set by EU law?*
5. *What legal or policy actions at the EU level could improve the coherence of Article 346 TFEU's application and contribute to greater strategic autonomy in the European defence sector?*

1.4. METHODOLOGY

This thesis primarily adopts a doctrinal research approach. The central objective is to analyze how Article 346 TFEU is applied in the field of defence procurement, with emphasis on legal reasoning and compliance with EU law. To support this core doctrinal analysis, the research also employs comparative, empirical, and normative methods. The comparison focuses on the Netherlands and Germany, examining how both Member States invoke and justify the use of the exemption. The empirical component consists of the collection and analysis of the invocations through expert interviews, national policy documents, and government communications. The data retrieved is used to examine and categorize the stated motivations for invoking Article 346. Normatively, the legality of the invocations and suggestions for reform will be researched. The research is library-based and relies on primary legal materials, academic literature, interviews, and national and EU policy documents. By combining doctrinal and supporting methods, the thesis aims to provide a structured and legally sound assessment of Article 346 in recent defence procurement policy.

The first sub-question is addressed solely through doctrinal legal research. This involves an analysis of Article 346 TFEU through jurisprudence of the Court, relevant interpretative communications by the European Commission, and academic literature. The objective is to clarify the legal framework that constrains or enables the invocation of Article 346.

The second and third sub-questions are addressed through comparative legal analysis, executed through empirical research and doctrinal legal research. The thesis examines the application of Article 346 TFEU in the Netherlands and Germany, focusing on two dimensions: (1) the formal legal and procedural framework, and (2) the application in practice of the provision in recent defence procurement in terms of the number of applications and the ground for invoking Article 346. The first dimension is researched with governmental and political documents, focusing on documents that are publicly available. For the second domain, there is a distinction in methodology between the Netherlands and Germany. As to the Netherlands, a significant number of projects to which Article 346 is applied, is disclosed through parliament, and regularly coupled with a brief argumentation on why Article 346 is invoked. These cases are catalogued in Annex I and empirically researched. By contrast, a different methodological approach is applied to the German case. In Germany, the budget committee must approve any contract with a value above EUR 25 million.³² However, none of these decisions or the underlying documentation is disclosed, leading to only a marginal number of invocations publicly known, which are shown in Annex II. Therefore, a number of written and spoken discussions have been held with academics and German legal practitioners. These discussions with different professionals provided information about the German policy towards Article 346.

³² Bundeshaushaltsordnung 1969, section 54(3); Wissenschaftliche Dienste des Deutschen Bundestages, 'Verträge mit einem Finanzvolumen von über 25 Millionen Euro im Geschäftsbereich des Bundesministeriums der Verteidigung: Zur Reichweite der Vorlagepflicht gegenüber dem Haushaltsausschuss' (Reference number: WD 3 - 3000 - 067/24, WD 4 - 3000 - 042/24, 2024).

Chapter 1

The fourth sub-question assesses how the national applications of Article 346 TFEU by the Netherlands and Germany align with the conditions for invocation established by the Court. This sub-question is addressed through a combination of comparative and normative doctrinal legal analysis. The comparative aspect is built upon the empirical and legal findings from the preceding two chapters. The normative dimension begs a legalistic interpretation of the justifications and practices found in each Member State, assessing their compatibility with the conditions established under Article 346.

The fifth sub-question is addressed through a normative doctrinal analysis. It examines whether the current approach to Article 346 TFEU can be reconciled with the objective of European strategic autonomy. This analysis builds on the preceding comparative findings and involves evaluating the existing national practices with broader EU integration goals and the intergovernmental framework of the EU.

In writing this thesis, limited use was made of artificial intelligence tools for four specific purposes. First, AI was used for brainstorming and conceptualizing the research to decide what direction the research would take. Second, during the writing process, AI has been utilized for providing suggestions on spelling, grammar, and structure. Thirdly, AI has been utilized to assist with citations in footnotes and the bibliography. Finally, the images on the front and back pages were generated through ChatGPT. The primary AI tools used were Grammarly and ChatGPT.

1.5. SCOPE

The thesis is delimited by a legal, functional, temporal, and financial scope to ensure feasibility of the research and comparability of procurement between Germany and the Netherlands.

1.5.1. LEGAL SCOPE

The legal scope is narrowed to the defence and security procurement exemption under Article 346 TFEU and its implementations in national law and secondary European law. While there are more exemptions in EU law besides Article 346, most importantly those in section 3 of the Directive and Articles 36, 51, 52, and 62 TFEU, these are excluded due to their distinct legal foundations and policy objectives. Section 3 of the Directive offers specific exclusions from the Directive's scope. These exclusions include contracts executed through international agreements or arrangements (Article 12) and contracts related to sensitive information, intelligence activities, and government-to-government sales (Article 13).³³ Two specific exclusions in these Articles are particularly significant. Firstly, the government-to-government procurement exclusion under Article 13(f) of the Directive permits Member States to award defence contracts directly to another government.³⁴ This mechanism is especially frequently utilized for procurements from the United States (US), as most equipment from the US takes place through the Foreign Military Sales program, which is a form of government-to-government procurement.³⁵ The Netherlands and Germany procured EUR 2.0 billion and EUR 4.6 billion worth of equipment, respectively, through the Foreign Military Sales

³³ Directorate-General for Internal Market and Services, 'Directive 2009/81/EC on the award of contracts in the fields of defence and security: Defence- and security-specific exclusions' (Guidance Note, European Commission 2010) <<https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/15408/attachments/1/translations/en/renditions/native>> accessed 27 June 2025.

³⁴ European Commission, 'Commission Notice: Guidance on the award of government-to-government contracts in the fields of defence and security (Article 13(f) of Directive 2009/81/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council)' [2016] OJ C450/1.

³⁵ Luke R. A. Butler, 'Transatlantic Defence Procurement: EU and US Defence Procurement Regulation in the Transatlantic Defence Market' (Cambridge University Press 2017), pp 392-415.

program between 2016 and July 2020.³⁶ Secondly, the international agreements exclusion under Articles 12 and 13(c) of the Directive makes contracts governed by procedural rules pursuant to an international agreement or arrangement fall outside the Directive's scope.³⁷ Nonetheless, these two exclusions can, and likely are, misused to circumvent the application of the Directive,³⁸ even though guidance notices were published in order to preclude the possibility of unjustified exclusions.³⁹ Including these provisions in the scope of this thesis would necessitate a broader analysis of various international agreements and specific contractual scenarios, which fall outside the intended focus on Article 346.

Moreover, Articles 36, 45, 52, and 65 TFEU provide exemptions with regard to public morality, public policy, public security, and the exercise of official authority. These provisions are concerned with the free movement of goods, services, capital, and persons within the internal market. However, Article 346 TFEU operates as *lex specialis*. Articles 45, 52, and 65, and especially Article 36, can, nevertheless, also affect procurement procedures, although their application is limited to situations where overriding public interests justify restrictions on fundamental freedoms.⁴⁰ Besides, Article 36 applies solely to goods that fall outside the scope of Article 346(1)(b) TFEU.⁴¹ Including these articles in the scope of this thesis would entail a broader analysis of internal market freedoms. By concentrating on Article 346, this thesis aims to provide a detailed examination of the legal framework governing defence and security procurement exemptions.

As a rule, this thesis in principle refers to the whole Article 346 TFEU in general, while most derogations in defence procurement are based on Article 346(1)(b) TFEU. The exemption of Article 346(1)(a) TFEU, which permits the withholding of information, plays only a relevant role in connection with safeguarding secrecy and confidentiality. Accordingly, this thesis, while saying 'Article 346' or 'Article 346 TFEU', focuses on Article 346(1)(b), with reference to Article 346(1)(a) only in the context of secrecy and confidentiality.

With regards to legal improvements, this research focuses on improvements through the intergovernmental framework of the Common Security and Defence Policy (CSDP) rather than through supranational internal market instruments. The Directive, adopted under Article 114 TFEU, was primarily justified on internal market grounds. However, defence procurement is directly related to objectives that are fundamentally ingrained in military logic and stand contrary to open market principles. This creates a mismatch between the legal basis and the functional objective of the measure. As Meershoek argued, the Directive was arguably adopted on the wrong legal basis.⁴² Possibly, the alignment of procurement rules with defence objectives would have been better achieved had the Directive been adopted within the CSDP framework, which also would have respected the constitutional division of competences in the EU.⁴³

³⁶ Loannides 2020 (n 5), p 110.

³⁷ European Commission, 'Commission notice on guidance on cooperative procurement in the fields of defence and security (Defence and Security Procurement Directive 2009/81/EC)' [2019] OJ C157/1.

³⁸ Butler 2017 (n 35) pp 127-133; Personal Communication with Martin Trybus (videocall, 6 May 2025).

³⁹ Directorate-General for Internal Market and Services 2010 (n 33); European Commission, 'Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions: Towards a more competitive and efficient defence and security sector' COM(2013) 542 final, section 2.1; European Commission 2016 (1).

⁴⁰ Martin Trybus, *Buying Defence and Security in Europe* (Cambridge University Press 2014), pp 71-73, 85.

⁴¹ *ibid.*

⁴² Meershoek 2022 (n 10), pp 369-373.

⁴³ *ibid.*, pp 359-361.

Chapter 1

1.5.2. FUNCTIONAL, TEMPORAL, AND FINANCIAL SCOPE

Functionally, this research focuses on government procurement of military equipment. The application of Article 346 TFEU extends beyond public procurement, and can be applied to any measures taken to protect essential national interests in the context of defence: for example, in the context of state aid,⁴⁴ citizenship requirements, and labor law requirements.⁴⁵ However, this thesis focuses on the application of Article 346 with regard to defence procurement. Within this domain, the thesis examines the grounds for the invocation of Article 346. These grounds are categorized as follows: (1) direct awards without, (2) direct awards with some form of competition, (3) offsets, (4) secrecy and confidentiality, and (5) urgency.

The temporal scope of this research ranges from 2020 to June 2025. This scope is justified because it includes all actions after the invasion of Ukraine in 2022, while not unnecessarily broadening the scope. Within this timeframe, sixteen concrete invocations of Article 346 TFEU have been analyzed: thirteen by the Netherlands and three by Germany, as well as three court cases which disclosed two more invocations by Germany.

For both countries, the financial scope is restricted to projects with a contract value above EUR 50 million. Although Germany's parliamentary oversight applies to contracts above EUR 25 million, this research adopts a unified threshold of EUR 50 million for both countries, as no invocation in Germany for a project below this threshold has been identified. The threshold is justified on two grounds. First, high-value procurement projects typically reflect deliberate strategic choices by national authorities. Second, such projects are more likely to have a systemic impact on the national DTIB, as well as the EDTIB, and are thus most relevant to the legal and policy implications of invoking Article 346 TFEU.

1.6. LIMITATIONS

Two limitations need to be addressed. A first limitation in this research concerns the scarcity of publicly available information about the invocation of Article 346 TFEU in defence procurement. Member States treat the application of this Article as a matter of national security, resulting in limited transparency and public disclosure. This lack of data poses challenges in conducting the analysis. This criticism is not new and was even expressed by the European Parliament.⁴⁶

As to the Netherlands, the country is relatively transparent, and the Minister of Defence (Minister) provides information on procurement practices, including instances where Article 346 TFEU is invoked. However, the Minister also made clear in parliament that not all invocations are shared, and that it does not want to disclose how often the exemption is applied.⁴⁷ It is not known how many projects Article 346 was applied to, and what value these projects represent. On the other hand, Germany maintains an even more secret stance regarding the application of Article 346 TFEU. Information on specific cases where Article 346 is invoked is generally not disclosed to the

⁴⁴ State aid is aid by the member state directly or indirectly financing a manufacturer. State aid is in principle prohibited by the EU legal framework comprising Articles 107-109 TFEU. However, state aid might be allowed under Article 346. See the following example of a case resulting from state aid awarded to civilian activities under Article 346 TFEU: Commission Decision (C 16/04) 2009/610/EC [2009] OJ L 225/104; Case C-485/10 *European Commission v Hellenic Republic* [2012] ECLI:EU:C:2012:395.

⁴⁵ Heuninx 2018 (n 19), pp 53-54.

⁴⁶ Loannides 2020 (n 5), pp 143-144.

⁴⁷ Plaatsvervangend directeur-generaal beleid, 'Beslisnota bij Antwoord op vragen van de leden Eerdmans en Tuinman over aanbestedingsbureaucratie bij defensieaankopen' (17 June 2024) <<https://www.tweedekamer.nl/kamerstukken/detail?id=2024D25408&did=2024D25408>> accessed 27 June 2025.

public, making it challenging to assess the implementation in practice of the exemption in the German context.

A second limitation concerns the Commission's proposal to amend the Directive from June 2025, which includes broadening the allowed derogations.⁴⁸ Whether the proposal will be adopted in this form, or at all, and how its changes will materially affect defence procurement practices remains to be seen. Consequently, aside from occasional discussion where relevant, the amendment is not incorporated into this thesis.

1.7. OUTLINE

This thesis is structured as follows.

Chapter 2 sets out the judicial principles and conditions of application of Article 346 TFEU, explaining how the provision operates, its material scope, and the conditions that must be met for a lawful invocation under EU law. This chapter also covers recent case law.

Chapters 3 and 4 analyze how Article 346 TFEU is applied in practice in the Netherlands and Germany, respectively. These chapters examine for each country separately (1) the security interests and defence industry, (2) the legal and administrative frameworks of invoking Article 346, (3) the number of invocations, and (4) the concrete grounds for invocations of Article 346. Case law will also be examined.

Chapter 5 brings the findings of the previous chapters together; the chapter firstly compares practical approaches and legal justifications of both countries and, secondly, evaluates their compliance with the principles of necessity and proportionality under EU law.

Chapter 6 places the findings in the broader debate on European strategic autonomy. It discusses legal and policy reforms that could improve coherence in the application of Article 346 TFEU without undermining national sovereignty. It will assess whether more coordinated practices, through soft law, interpretative guidelines, or cooperation via intergovernmental platforms, could support European strategic autonomy.

Finally, the conclusion will give an answer to the main research question of this thesis.

⁴⁸ European Commission, 'Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Directives 2009/43/EC and 2009/81/EC, as regards the simplification of intra-EU transfers of defence-related products and the simplification of security and defence procurement' COM(2025) 823 final.

CHAPTER 2. ESTABLISHED LEGAL FRAMEWORK OF ARTICLE 346 TFEU

Article 346 TFEU provides Member States with an exemption from EU law for measures taken to protect essential security interests. This chapter sets out the legal regime governing Article 346. Sections 2.1. to 2.6. provide an analysis of Article 346(1)(b) and 346(2) TFEU, and the conditions for their applicability as established by jurisprudence and academic commentary. Section 2.1. introduces the two Articles, after which sections 2.2. until 2.5. each discuss one criterion for invocation. Section 2.6. discusses the procedure against a Member State that applies the exemption improperly. Lastly, subsection 2.7 discusses Article 346(1)(a) TFEU, which addresses the non-disclosure of information contrary to a Member State's essential security interests.⁴⁹

2.1. ARTICLE 346(1)(b) TFEU

Article 346(1)(b) TFEU establishes the following:

*‘[A]ny Member State may take such measures as it considers **necessary for the protection of the essential interests of its security which are connected with the production of or trade in arms, munitions and war material; such measures shall not adversely affect the conditions of competition in the internal market regarding products which are not intended for specifically military purposes.**’*

This provision constitutes an exemption to the application of EU law as a whole. Article 346 TFEU should be viewed as an exceptional measure with its own regime. Through Article 346, the fundamental principles of non-discrimination and transparency in the field of public procurement, as established by internal market rules set by the TFEU, the Civil Public Procurement Directive,⁵⁰ and the Directive, do not have to be applied by member states.⁵¹ The exceptional nature of the clause means that it is interpreted restrictively and narrowly.⁵² The CJEU has consistently reiterated that derogations from the Treaty must be narrowly construed, and only invoked where no alternative mechanism suffices. Initially stated in *Johnston*,⁵³ the Court emphasized that derogations from the EU's treaties must be interpreted strictly to preserve coherence and effectiveness of EU law. This was also recently reiterated in *Commission v Austria*,⁵⁴ and *Commission v Poland*.⁵⁵ In these cases, the Court emphasized that the derogation under Article 346 applies only in exceptional and well-defined circumstances.

As a consequence, as to the burden of proof, it is for the Member State invoking Article 346 TFEU to provide convincing evidence that its application is lawful.⁵⁶ The Court confirmed this

⁴⁹ For general background reading besides the sources cited in this chapter, see additionally: Vincenzo Randazzo, ‘Article 346 and the Qualified Application of EU Law to Defence’ (European Union Institute for Security Studies 2014); Vilius Kuzminskas, ‘SESV Sutarties 346 Straipsnyje Įtvirtintos Išimties Taikymas Gynybos ir Saugumo Srities Viešiesiems Pirkimams’ (2018) 106 Teisė 144.

⁵⁰ Directive 2014/24/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 February 2014 on public procurement and repealing Directive 2004/18/EC [2014] OJ L94/65 (Directive 2014/24/EU).

⁵¹ Trybus 2014 (n 40), pp 85-135; Baudouin Heuinckx, *The Law of Collaborative Defence Procurement in the European Union* (Cambridge University Press 2016), pp 49-55; Heuinckx 2018 (n 19), p 53.

⁵² Trybus 2014 (n 40), pp 85-87; Heuinckx 2018 (n 19), p 52; Heuinckx 2018 (n 19), pp 61-62;

⁵³ Case C-222/84 *Johnston v Chief Constable of the Royal Ulster Constabulary* [1986] ECR 01651, para 26.

⁵⁴ Case C-187/16 *European Commission v Republic of Austria* [2018] ECLI:EU:C:2018:194, para 77.

⁵⁵ Case C-601/21 *European Commission v Republic of Poland* [2023] ECLI:EU:C:2023:629, para 81.

⁵⁶ Trybus 2014 (n 40), pp 119-120.

in *Spanish Weapons*,⁵⁷ as well as in more recent cases.⁵⁸ In practice, this further narrows the applicability of Article 346 and requires Member States to show that the derogation is necessary and limited to protecting essential security interests.

The application of Article 346(1)(b) TFEU is conditioned by the following four key elements:

1. Following from Article 346(2) TFEU, the measures taken under Article 346(1)(b) TFEU must be linked to ‘war material’ as defined by the list established in 1958 (1958 Arms List)⁵⁹ by the Council of the European Union (Council). This list is exhaustive, and dual-use items are not automatically covered. This first criterion establishes the Material Scope of Article 346(1)(b).
2. The measures must be related to the essential interests of the security of the state. This means that general assertions are insufficient, and a Member State must prove the connection between the measures taken and the essential interests of the state.
3. The measures taken must not distort competition in the internal market for civilian goods. Article 346(1)(b) TFEU operates as a last-resort option and applies only to war equipment included in the 1958 Arms List. This requirement primarily affects offset agreements, which can be market-distortive, and are generally prohibited unless justified under Article 346 TFEU.
4. The measures taken must be (1) necessary, meaning they must be essential for the protection of the Member State's essential security interests, and (2) proportionate, meaning that no less restrictive means are available to attain the result.

2.2. THE MATERIAL SCOPE

According to Article 346(2) TFEU, the scope of the derogation is tied to the specific list of war material as created by the Council on 15 April 1958.⁶⁰ This list defines the categories of military equipment to which the derogation applies. Only items explicitly included in the list benefit from the derogation under Article 346(1)(b) TFEU.⁶¹ In *Fiocchi Munizioni*,⁶² the Court ruled that the 1958 Arms List is not illustrative but constitutes a limitation on the material scope of Article 346 TFEU. However, the exemption is not limited to the purchase of the listed goods themselves. It also covers procurements involving essential security interests related to those goods. As early as 2006, the European Commission clarified that the exemption may also apply to services directly linked to listed goods and to ‘modern, capability-focused acquisition methods’.⁶³ Amending the list never happened, and the Council can amend the list only by unanimous decision, in line with the intergovernmental character of the Common Foreign and Security Policy.

Although the 1958 Arms List comprises fifteen categories of military goods, these categories are very broad descriptions of military equipment. Most importantly, this includes the

⁵⁷ *Commission of the European Communities v Kingdom of Spain* [1999] (n 4), paras 22-23.

⁵⁸ Case C-284/05 *Commission v Finland* [2009] ECLI:EU:C:2009:778, para 49; for more cases, see: Trybus 2014 (n 40), p 120.

⁵⁹ Council Decision 255/58 of 15 April 1958 defining the list of arms, munitions, and war material referred to in Article 346(1)(b) TFEU.

⁶⁰ European Commission, ‘Interpretative Communication on the application of Article 296 of the Treaty in the field of defence procurement’ COM(2006) 779 final, pp 5-6; Trybus 2014 (n 40), pp 88-94.

⁶¹ Heuninckx 2018 (n 19), p 61; Nicolas Pourbaix, ‘The Future Scope of Application of Article 346 TFEU’ (2011) 20 PPLR 1, p 5.

⁶² Case T-26/01 *Fiocchi Munizioni SpA v Commission* [2003] II-3951, paras 58–60.

⁶³ European Commission 2006 (n 60), p 6.

following categories: firearms, artillery, ammunition, bombs, tanks, toxic agents, warships, military aircraft, electronic and optical military equipment, and even ‘other equipment and material’ (later clarified to be parachutes, devices to cross water, and searchlights).⁶⁴

While one could expect the list to be outdated, the list has proven resilient.⁶⁵ The list’s broadly formulated categories are interpreted dynamically by the Court, and Recital 10 of the Directive even acknowledges a dynamic interpretation of the list, stating that ‘the list is generic and is to be interpreted broadly in the light of the evolving character of technology, military equipment, procurement policies and military requirements’. Nevertheless, there have been German calls to change and renew the list, although the German government also acknowledged that this is not feasible in the short term.⁶⁶

2.2.1. DUAL-USE EQUIPMENT

The question of whether procurement of dual-use equipment can be exempted under Article 346 TFEU has been legally delicate. The last phrase of Article 346(1)(b) TFEU states that dual-use equipment not specifically for military use falls outside the scope of Article 346. There have been several cases clarifying this issue.⁶⁷

In *Agusta*,⁶⁸ Italy argued that helicopters that were usable for both civilian and military purposes fell under Article 346(1)(b) TFEU. However, the Court rejected this view by ruling that products must be intended for specifically military purposes to fall within the scope of the derogation. Where military use is ‘hardly certain’,⁶⁹ as was the case with these helicopters that were also used in civilian roles, the procurement must comply with the Public Procurement Directive.⁷⁰ Moreover, the Opinion of AG in *Agusta* clearly stated that Article 346(1)(b) TFEU only applies to products on the 1958 Arms List, and that dual-use goods are not covered unless explicitly listed.⁷¹

While certain dual-use items do appear on the 1958 Arms List, like parachutes and detection equipment, their inclusion does not expand the scope of Article 346 TFEU to all dual-use products. Instead, a three-stage test is necessary: the item must (1) fall under a category on the list, (2) be intended for specifically military purposes (subjective test), and (3), in the *Finnish Turntables* case, the Court stated the requirement that even listed dual-use items factually must be ‘specifically designed and developed’ for military use (objective test).⁷² Thus, not only does the intent of military use of dual-use equipment on the 1958 Arms List suffice, but the dual-use equipment must also have special military characteristics.⁷³

⁶⁴ Trybus 2014 (n 40), pp 90-94; Andrea Sundstrand, ‘Article 346, EU Defence Procurement and the European Court of Justice’ [2023] *The Procurement Journal* 15, pp 17-18.

⁶⁵ Trybus 2014 (n 40), pp 93-94.

⁶⁶ Bundestag, ‘Antwort der Bundesregierung auf die Kleine Anfrage der Abgeordneten Dr. Reinhard Brandl u. a. und der Fraktion der CDU/CSU: Aufrechterhaltung der Sicherheits- und Verteidigungsindustrie in Deutschland’ (Drucksache 20/13937, 8 January 2025) <<https://dserver.bundestag.de/btd/20/139/2013937.pdf>> accessed 27 June 2025, pp 6-7; Bundestag, ‘Antwort der Bundesregierung auf die Kleine Anfrage der Fraktion der CDU/CSU: Digitale Souveränität in der Bundesverwaltung: Beschaffung und Einsatz von IT-(Sicherheits-)Produkten durch den Bund als öffentlichen Auftraggeber’ (Drucksache 20/14887, 4 February 2025) <<https://dserver.bundestag.de/btd/20/148/2014887.pdf>> accessed 27 June 2025, pp 23-24.

⁶⁷ Trybus 2014 (n 40), pp 94-103.

⁶⁸ Case C-337/05 *Commission of the European Communities v Italian Republic* [2008] ECR I-2173, paras 43–60.

⁶⁹ *ibid*, para 47.

⁷⁰ Directive 2014/24/EU.

⁷¹ Opinion of Advocate General Mazák in Case C-337/05 *Commission v Italy* [2007] ECR I-2173, para 59; Sundstrand 2023 (n 64), pp 18-19.

⁷² Case C-615/10 *Insinööri-toimisto InsTiimi Oy v Suomen Puolustusvoimien Teknillinen Tutkimuslaitos* [2012] ECLI:EU:C:2012:324, paras 40–46.

⁷³ Heuninckx 2018 (n 19), p 61; Sundstrand 2023 (n 64), pp 20-21.

2.3. SECURITY INTEREST

The second criterion in the application of Article 346(1)(b) TFEU is the requirement that the measure in question must protect an essential security interest of the Member State.⁷⁴ The security interests are to be determined by the Member States. In this phase, Member States enjoy considerable freedom under Article 4(2) TEU.⁷⁵ Publication of these security interests is not required, although most states do so.⁷⁶ While Member States do retain wide discretion in defining their essential security interests, this discretion is still limited: the concept of security interests is confined to threats to core state functions, and not extended to general interests like consumer protection or employment.⁷⁷ The interest cannot be presumed, and must be justified on a case-by-case basis.

Scholars have advocated for an obligation on Member States to determine and publish their security interests.⁷⁸ Such an obligation would be reasonable in light of the EU principle of legal certainty and legitimate expectations. Currently, however, there is no mandate on the publication of essential security interests.

2.4. INTERNAL MARKET

Thirdly, any measures that Member States take are only allowed to impact competition for products on the 1958 Arms List. This last criterion thus delineates the applicability of Article 346 TFEU strictly to military equipment, without spilling over into markets for products for civilian or dual-use.⁷⁹ This third criterion is particularly relevant in relation to offsets and state aid.

Offsets are requirements placed by a procurement authority on foreign suppliers to invest in or procure goods or services from the host country as a condition for awarding a defence contract. This is used to support the domestic industry and to increase the willingness of the population to invest in defence.⁸⁰ Nonetheless, offsets also distort competition and are inherently in conflict with European law. Offsets are presumed to violate internal market rules, especially the framework on the free movement of goods and services.⁸¹ Moreover, offsets are not allowed under the Defence directive.⁸²

Military offsets relating directly to the military goods or services might be allowed for under Article 346 TFEU, provided that they are cumulatively:

- strictly necessary considering the essential security interests;
- proportionate and do not go beyond what is necessary to achieve that interest;
- tied directly to the military procurement.⁸³

⁷⁴ European Commission 2006 (n 60), pp 4-5; Trybus 2014 (n 40), pp 108-113; Heuinckx 2018 (n 19), pp 59-60.

⁷⁵ *European Commission v Republic of Austria* [2018] (n 54), para 75; *European Commission v Republic of Poland* [2023] (n 55), para 76; Heuinckx 2018 (n 19), p 59.

⁷⁶ Heuinckx 2018 (n 14), p 59, footnote 78.

⁷⁷ *European Commission v Republic of Austria* [2018] (n 54), para 78; *European Commission v Republic of Poland* [2023] (n 55), para 82; European Commission 2006 (n 60), p 5; Heuinckx 2018 (n 19), p 59.

⁷⁸ Heuinckx 2018 (n 19), pp 59-60.

⁷⁹ European Commission 2006 (n 60), pp 6-7; Heuinckx 2018 (n 19), pp 62-63.

⁸⁰ Ben Magahy, Francisco Vilhena da Cunha and Mark Pyman, *Defence Offsets: Addressing the Risks of Corruption & Raising Transparency* (Transparency International-UK 2010), pp 7-13; Heuinckx 2018 (n 19), pp 51-55.

⁸¹ Heuinckx 2018 (n 19), p 56.

⁸² European Commission, 'Directive 2009/81/EC on the award of contracts in the fields of defence and security: Guidance Note: Offsets' (Guidance Note, 2016) <<https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/15413/attachments/1/translations/>> accessed 27 June 2025.

⁸³ Heuinckx 2018 (n 19), p 57.

Civilian offsets, direct and indirect, are not allowed in any instance under EU law since this violates the clause of Article 346 TFEU that states that measures ‘shall not adversely affect the conditions of competition in the common market regarding products which are not intended for specifically military purposes’. The European Commission reiterated this position in 2016, when the Commission emphasized that non-military offsets can never be justified under Article 346, as they inherently affect the civilian economy and, therefore, do not fall within the material scope of Article 346(1)(b) TFEU.⁸⁴

2.5. NECESSITY AND PROPORTIONALITY

Lastly, the measures taken must be both necessary and proportional to protect the essential security interest.⁸⁵ This means that it has to be established how the measures taken will protect the essential security interest of the Member State.⁸⁶ In *Spanish Weapons*, the Court reaffirmed that Article 346 TFEU cannot be used to justify an exemption from EU law based solely on a broad appeal to national security. Instead, the Member State must demonstrate that the derogation is necessary in light of a concrete threat to a specific essential security interest.⁸⁷ This case, reiterated by other recent cases,⁸⁸ establishes that the invocation of Article 346(1)(b) TFEU requires a detailed and fact-based justification.

Specifically, necessity is fulfilled when the measures are objectively and directly related to the security interest. While Article 346(1)(b) TFEU refers to measures ‘which a Member State considers necessary’, the Court has clarified that this language does not preclude judicial review.⁸⁹ The necessity of a derogation must therefore be assessed in light of the specific facts and context in which it is invoked.⁹⁰

Proportionality, in turn, requires that no less restrictive alternative is available that would ensure the needed level of protection for the Member State’s essential security interests. This criterion could be fulfilled if procurement under the Directive would endanger the security interests of the state.⁹¹ The assessment must be based on concrete evidence rather than general or speculative claims. And even when Article 346 TFEU is legally invoked, the least restrictive measure must still be taken. This means, for example, that direct awards under competition through Article 346 must be preferred over direct awards without competition. However, the strictness of this proportionality

⁸⁴ European Commission 2016 (2) (n 82), pp 6-7.

⁸⁵ *European Commission v Republic of Austria* [2018] (n 54), para 75; *European Commission v Republic of Poland* [2023] (n 55), para 80; European Commission 2006 (n 60), pp 6-7; *Trybus* 2014 (n 40), pp 110-114; *Heuninckx* 2018 (n 19), pp 61-62.

⁸⁶ *Pourbaix* 2011 (n 61), pp 6-7.

⁸⁷ *Commission of the European Communities v Kingdom of Spain* [1999] (n 4), para 22.

⁸⁸ *European Commission v Republic of Austria* [2018] (n 54), para 76; *European Commission v Republic of Poland* [2023] (n 55), para 80.

⁸⁹ *Trybus* 2014 (n 40), p 114.

⁹⁰ See in this regard also the following two Belgian cases: *Heckler & Koch/Belgische Staat* [2024] nr. 240.651, Conseil d’État and *Heckler & Koch/Belgische Staat* [2024] nr. 260.296, Conseil d’État. In these two cases about the same tender, the Conseil d’État ruled that a 20-year term and exclusivity of an arms partnership contract was in line with the conditions of Article 346 TFEU. The Court stated that Belgium had examined less restrictive alternatives and concluded that only a long-term strategic partnership could guarantee delivery and maintain its defence industrial base.

⁹¹ Fabien Terpan and Sabine Saurugger, ‘Assessing Judicial Activism of the CJEU: The Case of the Court’s Defence Procurement Rulings’ (2018) 41 *Journal of European Integration* 543, p 550.

test in practice remains debatable, and in recent case law at the Court, no proportionality test was executed.⁹²

2.6. ENFORCEMENT PROCEDURE AGAINST ABUSE

Concerning the procedure of nationally applying Article 346 TFEU, this remains free to the Member States and is not determined by EU law. Member States are under no obligation to notify the European Commission or another authority in advance when they intend to rely on Article 346 procuring military equipment.⁹³ Similarly to the publication of essential security interests, one could think of an obligation on Member States to determine and publish their administrative procedure for invoking Article 346.⁹⁴ However, currently, no such instrument, mandating a published pre-determined procedure, exists.

Article 348 TFEU establishes a special public procedure to resolve disputes around the use of Article 346 TFEU.⁹⁵ It consists of two stages: first, following from paragraph 1, bilateral consultations between the Commission and the Member State have to be executed; second, following paragraph 2, the Commission and the Member States have the possibility of bringing the matter directly before the Court. Starting this procedure is optional, unlike in state aid cases, where the procedure of Article 108 TFEU is obligatory. The optional nature was restated in *Fiocchi Munizioni*,⁹⁶ when the Court clarified that the Commission is not obligated to use Article 348 but has discretion to decide whether a Member State's reliance on Article 346 TFEU is credible.

Besides review under Article 348 TFEU, the standard infringement procedure under Article 258 TFEU enables the Commission to start infringement proceedings whenever a Member State is alleged to have failed in its obligations under EU law.⁹⁷ Crucially, Article 348 can be applied only when the Commission expressly alleges illegal use of Article 346 TFEU without connecting this to other obligations under EU law; in the latter scenario, the regular enforcement route under Article 258 applies. Historically, most infringement actions related to Article 346 were litigated under Article 258.⁹⁸

Besides the public procedure, private procedures are also possible between the Member State and a private party. This can occur when a party alleges that an incorrect procurement procedure was followed by the government. Such actions are available under national law in the Member States, including in the Netherlands and Germany.⁹⁹ During these proceedings, the national court in the Member State can ask a preliminary question, which still allows the European Court to clarify Article 346 TFEU.

⁹² *European Commission v Republic of Austria* [2018] (n 54); *European Commission v Republic of Poland* [2023] (n 55); although these two cases concern Article 346(1)(a) TFEU, the proportionality test is similar, as will be explained in section 2.7.

⁹³ Trybus 2014 (n 40), pp 121-122.

⁹⁴ Heuninckx 2018 (n 19), pp 59-60.

⁹⁵ Trybus 2014 (n 40), pp 122-125.

⁹⁶ *Fiocchi Munizioni SpA* [2003] (n 62), para 74.

⁹⁷ Trybus 2014 (n 40), pp 118-119, 122-125.

⁹⁸ *ibid*; Also the two latest cases on the use of 346 TFEU were brought to the court under Article 258 TFEU by the Commission: *European Commission v Republic of Austria* [2018] (n 54); *European Commission v Republic of Poland* [2023] (n 55).

⁹⁹ For Dutch law, see: Inger de Ru, 'Rechtsbescherming' (*Europa decentraal*) <<https://europadecentraal.nl/onderwerp/aanbesteden/aankondiging-tot-gunning/rechtsbescherming/>> accessed 27 June 2025; For German law, see: BLOMSTEIN, 'When & How to Challenge Defence Single Source Contracts' (*Blomstein*, 20 March 2024) <<https://www.blomstein.com/en/news/when-how-to-challenge-defence-single-source-contracts>> accessed 27 June 2025; besides, private procedures on alleged illegal use of Article 346 TFEU will be discussed in section 4.3.

2.7. ARTICLE 346(1)(a) TFEU

Article 346(1)(a) TFEU establishes the following:

‘[N]o Member State shall be obliged to supply information the disclosure of which it considers contrary to the essential interests of its security’

Article 346(1)(a) TFEU provides Member States with the discretion to withhold information which disclosure they consider contrary to their essential security interests. Similar to Article 346(1)(b) TFEU, the court has emphasized that the derogation from EU law must be interpreted strictly and applied only in exceptional and clearly defined cases. Necessity and proportionality of the measure must be satisfied to legally invoke the provision.¹⁰⁰ This provision thereby is a broad derogation from EU law, allowing member states to be exempt from the general obligation under EU law to supply information to EU institutions, as stipulated in Article 337 TFEU and the principle of sincere cooperation in Article 4(3) TEU. In defence procurement, this provision is relevant when the application of EU procurement rules would necessitate the disclosure of sensitive information.¹⁰¹

Member States invoking this exemption bear the burden of proof to demonstrate that the disclosure of specific information would indeed compromise their essential security interests. Besides the case discussed in the next section, Article 346(1)(a) TFEU was also invoked in the case *Australia v. Commission*.¹⁰² In this case, Austria sought to exempt the production of sensitive documents such as identity cards and passports from EU procurement law so that it could exclude foreign producers. However, the Court rejected Austria’s justification, and found that Austria had failed to demonstrate that less restrictive means, like using secure tendering procedures or imposing confidentiality requirements, would not have sufficiently protected its interests. Therefore, proportionality was not fulfilled.¹⁰³

The difference between Article 346(1)(a) TFEU and Article 346(1)(b) TFEU is that Article 346(1)(a) allows Member States to withhold information if they believe that doing so would harm their essential security interests. It is a passive safeguard, applicable to all government actions. In contrast, Article 346(1)(b) TFEU permits Member States to take active measures to protect security interests, but only in connection with equipment on the 1958 Arms List.¹⁰⁴ That said, in the context of secrecy and confidentiality measures in defence procurement, the distinction between the two provisions is not always significant in practice, as both require that the measures serve essential security interests and meet the conditions of necessity and proportionality.

Although Article 346(1)(a) TFEU has received less scholarly discourse, it is nevertheless implemented in the Defence Procurement Directive through Article 13(1), which excludes contracts covered by Article 346(1)(a) from the Directive’s scope.

2.8. RECENT CASE LAW

Since the start of the Russian invasion of Ukraine, the Court has handled only one case in 2023 on Article 346 TFEU: *European Commission v Poland*.¹⁰⁵ This case concerned the application of

¹⁰⁰ Trybus 2014 (n 40), pp 128-133.

¹⁰¹ *ibid*, p 129.

¹⁰² *European Commission v Republic of Austria* [2018] (n 54).

¹⁰³ *ibid*, para 96.

¹⁰⁴ Directorate-General for Internal Market and Services 2010 (n 33), pp 4-5.

¹⁰⁵ *European Commission v Republic of Poland* [2023] (n 55).

Article 346(1)(a) TFEU, and Poland invoked Article 346 against the Commission in an infringement procedure under Article 258 TFEU.

Polish law¹⁰⁶ exempted certain service contracts, such as the production of identity documents, excise stamps, legal markings, ballot papers, and electronic systems managing public documents, from public procurement procedures under Directive 2014/24/EU.¹⁰⁷ These contracts were directly awarded to the state-owned firm PWPW without conducting any tender. Poland justified this exemption by invoking Article 346(1)(a) TFEU, stating that supplying the information gives rise to unacceptable risks of leakage which would threaten the essential security interests of the state.¹⁰⁸ Poland argued that the confidentiality and integrity of these documents and the personal data they contain constituted essential security interests that could not be protected through a competitive tender. However, the Commission argued that Poland failed to show that the protection of its security interests could not be ensured through less restrictive means within the procurement framework of Directive 2014/24/EU.¹⁰⁹

In its judgement, the Court ruled that Poland violated the Civil Procurement Directive by directly awarding contracts for all documents under Article 3(5c) of the law on public procurement without a competitive tender.¹¹⁰ However, interestingly, the court does accept the use of Article 346(1)(a) TFEU for all information related to military personnel and security officers. The Court justifies this exception by stating that these documents are so closely and directly related to national security interests that a leakage could result in irreparable harm to national security.¹¹¹ The documents for this specific group of people contain highly sensitive information that, if leaked, would expose the society to ‘third States or, in particular, by criminal gangs or terrorist organisations’.¹¹² Unlike other public documents, the production of these security-related documents could not, according to the Court, be sufficiently safeguarded merely through confidentiality obligations imposed in a public procurement process under Directive 2014/24/EU. Poland, in its argumentation, explicitly stated that the ‘current international context’ resulting from the war in Ukraine and Poland’s membership of the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) increased the need for supervision on information.¹¹³ Although the Court did not explicitly tie its legal reasoning to the geopolitical situation, the Court was mindful of the deteriorating security environment in Europe and its potential impact on national security assessments.

Therefore, I would argue that this case is an example of the more lenient approach to Article 346 TFEU by the Court, especially with regard to proportionality and necessity in defence procurement. The deteriorated security situation in Europe forces Member States to be more protective and cautious concerning information disclosure.

2.9. INTERIM-CONCLUSION

This chapter outlined the legal framework governing Article 346 TFEU. While Article 346(1)(b) TFEU allows Member States to derogate from EU procurement law to protect essential security

¹⁰⁶ Ustawa Prawo zamówień publicznych 2019, art 3(5c).

¹⁰⁷ *ibid*, para 2.

¹⁰⁸ *ibid*, paras 39-67.

¹⁰⁹ *ibid*, paras 23-39.

¹¹⁰ *ibid*, para 123; Directive 2014/24/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 February 2014 on public procurement [2014] OJ L94/65.

¹¹¹ *European Commission v Republic of Poland* [2023] (n 55), para 107-111.

¹¹² *ibid*, para 109; The original quotation uses British English spelling (‘organisations’). Elsewhere in this text, American English spelling is used.

¹¹³ *ibid*, para 46.

Established Legal Framework of Article 346 TFEU

interests, the Court has consistently held that it must be interpreted strictly and applied only in exceptional cases. The four key conditions for lawful invocation are: (1) the material scope, (2) the existence of an essential security interest, (3) the absence of market distortions, and (4) the proportionality and necessity of the measure. Conditions 2 and 4 apply equally to Article 346(1)(a) TFEU, which allows Member States to withhold sensitive information.

CHAPTER 3. THE NETHERLANDS

Having discussed the legal framework of Article 346 TFEU, chapter 3 examines the application of Article 346 by the Netherlands. Section 3.1. first examines how the Dutch government defines its essential security interests and what the key actors in the Dutch Defence Technological and Industrial Base (NLDTIB) are, as these definitions and actors to a large extent inform one of when Article 346 can be legally invoked. Section 3.2. discusses the legal and administrative procedures established for invoking Article 346. Section 3.3. analyzes the number of invocations and the effect of the war in Ukraine on the number. The section also discusses the financial value of the invocations. Lastly, section 3.4. analyzes the grounds for the invocations.

3.1. ESSENTIAL SECURITY INTERESTS

In the Netherlands, the delineation of ‘essential security interests’ for the purposes of invoking Article 346(1)(b) TFEU is shaped by a framework that includes several policy documents; most importantly, those are the *Security Strategy*,¹¹⁴ the *Defence White Paper 2024*,¹¹⁵ the *Defence Industry Strategie* (2018),¹¹⁶ an update from 2022 as a consequence of the Russian invasion of Ukraine,¹¹⁷ and the *Defence Strategy for Industry and Innovation 2025–2029*.¹¹⁸ These documents, taken together, provide a comprehensive overview of the national interests deemed vital for the state's security.

The *Security Strategy* identifies six national security interests: territorial security, physical security, economic security, ecological security, social and political stability, and international legal order and stability.¹¹⁹ The Security Strategy emphasizes a holistic ‘all-hazards’ approach, in line with the indivisibility of internal and external security.¹²⁰ The Security Strategy identifies seven threats: geopolitical threats, hybrid threats, climate threats, social threats, threats to the democratic legal order, strategic infrastructure and economic dependency threats, and technological and digital threats.¹²¹ This framework thus not only defines national security in the context of military physical threats, but also the context of societal resilience and hybrid threats to sovereignty through, for example, digital warfare or externally organized weakening of democratic institutions.

In 2024, the Ministry of Defence (Ministry) published the *2024 Defence White Paper*, in which the Minister communicated his priorities for the Dutch military. As to essential security interests, the White Paper underlines strategic rivalry between superpowers, hybrid threats, technological and digital threats, and border threats.¹²² The Netherlands defines the task of the

¹¹⁴ Government of the Netherlands, ‘Security Strategy for the Kingdom of the Netherlands’ (2023) <<https://www.government.nl/topics/security-strategy-for-the-kingdom-of-the-netherlands/documents/publications/2023/04/03/security-strategy-for-the-kingdom-of-the-netherlands>> accessed 27 June 2025.

¹¹⁵ Ministry of Defence, ‘Defence White Paper 2024’ (2024) <<https://english.defensie.nl/downloads/publications/2024/09/05/defence-white-paper-2024>> accessed 27 June 2025.

¹¹⁶ Ministry of Defence and the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy 2018 (n 28).

¹¹⁷ *Kamerstukken II* 2022-2023, 31125, nr. 123.

¹¹⁸ Ministry of Defence and the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy 2018 (n 28); *Kamerstukken II* 2022-2023, 31125, nr. 123; Ministry of Defence, ‘Defence Strategy for Industry and Innovation 2025–2029’ (2025) <<https://english.defensie.nl/downloads/policy-notes/2025/04/04/defence-strategy-for-industry-and-innovation-2025-2029>> accessed 27 June 2025.

¹¹⁹ Government of the Netherlands 2023 (n 114), pp 12, 41.

¹²⁰ *ibid*, pp 4-5, 7.

¹²¹ *ibid*, pp 13-19.

¹²² Ministry of Defence 2024 (1) (n 115), pp 8-13.

Dutch defence to be able to credibly defend the Netherlands and protect international stability.¹²³ A strong deterring defence is established through a combination of digital transformation, international cooperation, a strong national industry, and strong innovation.¹²⁴ In the White Paper, security interests encompass the readiness of the armed forces to defend national and NATO territory, secure strategic autonomy, and maintain operational continuity in case of disruptions to supply chains, cyber-infrastructure, and industrial capacity.¹²⁵

The *Defence Industry Strategy* (2018),¹²⁶ the updated *Defence Industry Strategy in a New Geopolitical Context* (2022),¹²⁷ and the recently published *Defence Strategy for Industry and Innovation 2025-2029*¹²⁸ identify the industrial-technological capabilities that the Dutch government regards as essential to national security. These documents identify the sectors in which offsets or direct awards might play a role in supporting the Dutch defence industry, which are only legal when the exemption under Article 346 TFEU can be invoked.¹²⁹ In the *Defence Strategy* (2018), the Minister also explicitly states that Article 346 is invoked to support the NLDTIB. The Minister states that the NLDTIB should be involved in the international supply chain, and the Minister wants to actively favor the Dutch industry in order to strengthen the NLDTIB.¹³⁰ Although this is not as explicitly mentioned in the *Defence Strategy 2025-2029*, this does not mean that Article 346 cannot be as frequently invoked in the future.

Concerning specific industrial capabilities, the *Defence Strategy for Industry and Innovation 2025-2029* sets out the goals for the NLDTIB. Moreover, the *Defence Strategy 2025-2029* defines five fundamental defence areas in which the Netherlands wants to innovate: intelligent systems, smart materials, space, sensors, and quantum.¹³¹ On international cooperation, the *Defence Strategy 2025-2029* expresses a preference for working first at the European level, then within NATO, and lastly with other international partners.¹³² The EU as a defence partner is mentioned, but mainly in connection to funding channels. The importance of national capabilities in the maritime industry stands out. Although the 2025-2029 *Defence Strategy* does not yet specifically define the current essential security interest to the extent that the *Defence Strategy* (2018) does, the Ministry is working on an extension of the *Defence Strategy 2025-2029* that also defines the Dutch essential security interest.¹³³

The *Defence Strategy* (2018) defined eleven technologies and ten knowledge areas, and nine industrial capabilities.¹³⁴ For each of these domains, the *Defence Strategy* (2018) prescribes a different level of autonomy desired. However, the government wants the Netherlands to be almost fully capable of five industrial-technological capabilities: autonomously producing maritime main weapon systems,¹³⁵ intelligence systems, communication systems, support systems and logistical support systems. Not only was the importance of the maritime industry emphasized in the *Defence Strategy* (2018), but this was also reiterated in the *Defence Strategy in a new Geopolitical Context*

¹²³ *ibid*, pp 8, 21-22.

¹²⁴ *ibid*, pp 8, 25-33.

¹²⁵ *ibid*, pp 35-41.

¹²⁶ Ministry of Defence and the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy 2018 (n 28).

¹²⁷ *Kamerstukken II 2022-2023*, 31125, nr. 123.

¹²⁸ Ministry of Defence 2025 (1) (n 118).

¹²⁹ European Commission 2006 (n 60), p 7; European Commission 2016 (2) (n 82).

¹³⁰ Ministry of Defence and the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy 2018 (n 28), pp 31-32.

¹³¹ Ministry of Defence 2025 (1) (n 118), pp 17-22.

¹³² *ibid*, p 28.

¹³³ Personal communication with Jorn Bleijs (Utrecht, 22 May 2024).

¹³⁴ Ministry of Defence and the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy 2018 (n 28), p 17.

¹³⁵ One could think of frigates and submarines.

(2022), and the *Sectoragenda Maritieme Maakindustrie*.¹³⁶ These publications emphasize the necessary support for the maritime industry through Article 346 TFEU and outline the objective of strengthening and expanding the use of Article 346 in the future. For the air force, on the other hand, the Netherlands cooperates strongly with the US, and for ground forces, the Netherlands cooperates primarily with Germany.¹³⁷ But even in the maritime sector, the Netherlands also cooperates with other countries, as is shown by the two collective procurement projects with Belgium.¹³⁸

An important addition is that maritime capabilities are warranted not only for the Dutch sea border in Europe, but also for the sea border of the Netherlands Antilles.¹³⁹ According to the overarching Charter for the Kingdom,¹⁴⁰ the Dutch armed forces are responsible for the defence of all its territory, thus necessitating marine capabilities to defend the islands.¹⁴¹ The defence of the Netherlands Antilles is also stressed throughout the Security Strategy.¹⁴² Further strengthening the need for maritime defence is the fact that these Caribbean territories are not covered by the collective defence clause of Article 5 of the NATO Treaty,¹⁴³ as the geographical scope of NATO's mutual defence commitment is limited to attacks 'on the territory of any of the Parties in Europe or North America', and 'on the islands under the jurisdiction of any of the Parties in the North Atlantic area north of the Tropic of Cancer', as defined by Article 6 of the Treaty. As a result, an armed attack against the Netherlands Antilles would not automatically trigger allied support. This exclusion increases the responsibility of the Netherlands to ensure the sovereignty of the islands independently.

From these three documents, several overarching essential interests can be distilled that are likely to arise during defence procurement:

1. the capability to act autonomously in operational terms within the Netherlands, including in light of the Netherlands Antilles, whose territory is not protected by the NATO alliance;
2. the autonomy of the maritime Dutch defence industry;
3. the cooperation with Germany for land material and the US for air material;
4. protection against hybrid, digital threats, and socio-economic threats;
5. the ability to execute NATO obligations;
6. innovation of the NLDTIB in certain specific and fundamental defence areas.

¹³⁶ Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy, 'Sectoragenda Maritieme Maakindustrie' (2023) <<https://open.overheid.nl/documenten/700c6d90-4922-4ad5-ab4c-448853015fee/file>> accessed 27 June 2025, pp 44, 52-53, 58.

¹³⁷ Nathan Meershoek, 'Dutch Defence Procurement in Times of War and Reinvestment' (2023) 32 Public Procurement Law Review 408, pp 412-413; Dick Zandee, 'Defence Procurement Practices? The Dutch Case' (Clingendael Institute 2024) <https://www.clingendael.org/sites/default/files/2024-10/Defence_Procurement_Practises_Netherlands_Commentary_DickZandee_0.pdf> accessed 27 June 2025.

¹³⁸ The projects *Vervanging M-fregatten (ASWF)* and *Vervanging mijnenbestrijdingscapaciteit (MCM)* are procured together with Belgium. For *Vervanging M-fregatten (ASWF)*, see Annex I; for *Vervanging mijnenbestrijdingscapaciteit (MCM)*, see Ministry of Defence, 'Defensie Projectenoverzicht 2024' (Ministry of Defence, 2024) <<https://www.defensie.nl/downloads/publicaties/2024/05/15/defensie-projectenoverzicht-2024>> accessed 27 June 2025, pp 57-58.

¹³⁹ The Netherlands Antilles are a group of three municipalities (Bonaire, Sint Eustatius and Saba) and three constituent countries (Aruba, Curaçao and Sint Maarten), united within the Kingdom of the Netherlands under the Charter for the Kingdom of the Netherlands.

¹⁴⁰ Statuut voor het Koninkrijk der Nederlanden 1954.

¹⁴¹ Ministry of Defence, 'Taken in het Caribisch gebied', (*defensie.nl*) <<https://www.defensie.nl/onderwerpen/taken-in-nederland/caribisch-gebied/taken-caribisch-gebied>> accessed 27 June 2025.

¹⁴² Government of the Netherlands, 2023 (n 114).

¹⁴³ North Atlantic Treaty (opened for signature 4 April 1949, entered into force 24 August 1949) 34 UNTS 243.

3.1.1. DUTCH DEFENCE TECHNOLOGICAL AND INDUSTRIAL BASE

It is also important to look at the actors in the NLDITB, since the essential security interests are inextricably linked to the industry. The Netherlands boasts a technologically advanced defence sector, albeit not very big, with an economic output of EUR 7.7 billion in 2023,¹⁴⁴ comprising approximately 1,000 companies and employing around 20,000 full-time equivalents directly employed within the sector.¹⁴⁵ In 2019, the Netherlands was the world's eleventh biggest exporter of defence equipment,¹⁴⁶ exporting equipment worth around EUR 1.5 billion per year.¹⁴⁷ Two key players in the Dutch defence industry include:

- Thales Nederland: as a subsidiary of the French Thales Group, Thales Nederland specializes in advanced naval systems, including radar, fire control, and communication systems. As of 2024, Thales Nederland had an annual revenue of approximately EUR 700 million, and it employs around 3000 people.¹⁴⁸
- Damen Shipyards Group: Damen is a Dutch shipbuilding company and constructs a broad range of vessels; this includes, for example, frigates, corvettes, patrol boats, and support ships. Its subsidiary, Damen Naval, focuses specifically on military naval vessels for the navy and international clients. As of 2024, Damen Shipyards group reported a record revenue of EUR 3.1 billion in 2023, and Damen Naval specifically employs approximately 1,200 people.¹⁴⁹

Beyond the big players,¹⁵⁰ SMEs are integral to the supply chain and provide specialized products and services. The Dutch SMEs bundle their interests in interest groups like the Netherlands Industries for Defence and Security,¹⁵¹ the Confederation of Netherlands Industry and Employers,¹⁵² and the Association of Mechanical and Electrical Engineering.¹⁵³ These industry associations play an important role in representing and supporting these military SMEs. To strengthen the ties between the Ministry and the defence industry, the Ministry, together with these three interest groups, established Defport in March 2025 as a new public-private organization to implement the governmental industrial strategies.¹⁵⁴

¹⁴⁴ Ministry of Defence 2025 (1) (n 118), p 18.

¹⁴⁵ Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy, 'Dutch Defence and Security related Technological and Industrial Base' (2022) <<https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&opi=89978449&url=https://www.government.nl/binaries/government/documenten/reports/2022/05/31/dutch-defence-and-security-related-technological-and-industrial-base/Dutch%2Bdefense%2Bband%2Bsecurity%2BTechnological%2Bband%2BIndustrial%2BBase.pdf&ved=2ahUKEwiIgeOrm9GNAXVFgf0HHYpQGyUQFnoECBcQAQ&usq=AovVaw1Rup1UrfHSqkhad1HnnZcu>> accessed 27 June 2025, slides 11, 16.

¹⁴⁶ Loannides 2020 (n 5), p 121.

¹⁴⁷ Government of the Netherlands, 'Commissariat for Military Production' (*Government of the Netherlands*) <<https://www.government.nl/topics/commissariat-for-military-production>> accessed 27 June 2025.

¹⁴⁸ Thales Group, 'Thales Nederland' (Thales) <<https://www.thalesgroup.com/en/countries/europe/netherlands>> accessed 27 June 2025.

¹⁴⁹ Business Focus Magazine 'Damen Naval: Mission Ready: Interview with Managing Director, Roland Briene' (*Business Focus*, 11 Oct 2024) <<https://businessfocusmagazine.com/2024/10/11/damen-naval-mission-ready/>> accessed 27 June 2025; Damen Shipyards Group, 'We are Damen' (Damen) <<https://www.damen.com/about>> accessed 27 June 2025.

¹⁵⁰ Besides the two largest companies mentioned, there are other major players slightly smaller in scale, such as Defenture, Fokker Technologies, and Van Halteren Technologies.

¹⁵¹ NIDV, see: <<https://www.nidv.eu/en/home/>> accessed 27 June 2025.

¹⁵² VNO-NCW, see: <<https://www.vno-ncw.nl/>>

¹⁵³ FME, see: <<https://www.fme.nl/>>

¹⁵⁴ Rijksoverheid, 'Op weg naar snellere productie en levering militair materieel' (*Rijksoverheid*, 25 March 2025) <<https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/actueel/nieuws/2025/03/25/op-weg-naar-snellere-productie-en-levering-militair-materieel>> accessed 27 June 2025; Ministry of Defence 2025 (1) (n 118), pp 24-25.

3.2. LEGAL AND ADMINISTRATIVE PROCEDURE OF INVOKING ARTICLE 346 TFEU

In the Netherlands, there is no formalized legal or administrative procedure codified for invoking Article 346(1)(b) TFEU. The decision to apply the clause is left to the discretion of the Ministry. The Defence Strategy (2018) emphasizes that for each procurement, the most suitable procurement procedure is selected with a view to balancing national security interests and compliance with European law.¹⁵⁵ It also notes that Article 346 TFEU may be used where European procurement rules do not offer sufficient safeguards for vital national interests, particularly in relation to the protection of strategic industrial and technological capabilities.¹⁵⁶

The Ministry can invoke Article 346 TFEU for any project with an essential security interest involved. Additionally, for any project exceeding EUR 5 million, the Ministry and the Commissariat for Military Production of the Ministry of Economic Affairs determine whether it would be in the Netherlands' interest to involve the NLDTIB in a purchase through offsets.¹⁵⁷

When it appears that offsets might benefit the Dutch industry, there is a standard procedure. In this case, the Ministry first enters into a contract with the targeted manufacturer of military equipment, a so-called International Cooperation Agreement. With this agreement, the manufacturer pledges that if it is awarded a military project, it will involve the Dutch industry to the extent agreed upon.¹⁵⁸ This can involve a considerable amount of funds, as is the case in the submarine project, in which EUR 1.0 billion was agreed upon through an international participation contract before awarding the actual submarine contract.¹⁵⁹ Also in parliament, there have been calls for more extensive use of Article 346 TFEU.¹⁶⁰

There is no legal obligation to report or notify either the European Commission or the Dutch Parliament when Article 346 TFEU is invoked. That said, a democratic check exists for major defence acquisitions. When a procurement project exceeds the threshold of EUR 50 million, the Minister is required to inform Parliament through a so-called A-brief. In principle, this brief only explains the desire and need for a certain procurement, and at this stage, the procurement route has not yet been determined. Normally, the Minister does not have to inform parliament later of the progress of any procurement under EUR 250 million. For projects containing certain risks, and projects above this financial range, the Minister must also inform parliament at later stages of the project.¹⁶¹ In these so-called B/C/D-briefs, the legal basis for the procurement can be disclosed.¹⁶²

¹⁵⁵ Ministry of Defence and the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy 2018 (n 28), pp 28, 31-32.

¹⁵⁶ *ibid.*

¹⁵⁷ *Kamerstukken II 2021-2022*, 26231, nr. 35; Ministry of Defence 2025 (1) (n 118), p 32.

¹⁵⁸ Commissariaat Militaire Productie, 'Industriële participatie (IP) militaire goederen' (Rijksoverheid) <<https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/onderwerpen/commissariaat-militaire-productie/industriële-participatie-ip-militaire-goederen>> accessed 27 June 2025.

¹⁵⁹ Defence Industry Europe, 'Netherlands: contract with Naval Group for Orka-class submarines officially signed' (*Defence Industry Europe*, 30 September 2024) <<https://defence-industry.eu/netherlands-contract-with-naval-group-for-orka-class-submarines-officially-signed/>> accessed 27 June 2025; Rijksoverheid, 'Nieuwe onderzeeboten forse impuls voor Nederlandse maritieme industrie' (*Rijksoverheid*, 15 March 2024) <<https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/actueel/nieuws/2024/03/15/nieuwe-onderzeeboten-forse-impuls-voor-nederlandse-maritieme-industrie>> accessed 27 June 2025.

¹⁶⁰ Tweede Kamer der Staten-Generaal, 'Jaarverslag en slotwet Ministerie van Defensie 2023' (15 mei 2024) <<https://www.tweedekamer.nl/kamerstukken/detail?id=2024D11355&did=2024D11355>> accessed 27 June 2025, p 17; *Kamerstukken II 2023-2024*, 36560-X, nr. 10; *Kamerstukken II 2023-2024*, 36600-X, nr. 4, p 9.

¹⁶¹ Ministry of Defence, 'Defensie Projectenoverzicht 2025' (Ministry of Defence 2025) <<https://www.defensie.nl/downloads/publicaties/2025/05/21/defensie-projectenoverzicht-2025>> accessed 27 June 2025, p 8.

¹⁶² Ministry of Defence, 'Defensie Materieel Proces bij de tijd' (Ministerie van Defensie 2017) <<https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/documenten/brochures/2017/02/01/defensie-materieel-proces-bij-de-tijd>> accessed 27 June 2025.

However, in practice, the precise legal basis for derogation is not always explicitly mentioned in these briefs.

3.3. INVOCATIONS OF ARTICLE 346 TFEU

Having discussed the Dutch essential security interests, the Dutch defence industry, and the procedure to invoke Article 346 TFEU, the historic invocations will be analyzed. Specifically, section 3.3.1. discusses the effect of the Russian invasion of Ukraine on the number of Invocations, and section 3.3.2. discusses the financial value of the invocations.

3.3.1. IMPACT OF THE INVASION OF UKRAINE ON THE NUMBER OF INVOCATIONS

There are signs the Netherlands has invoked Article 346 TFEU more frequently, not only absolutely, but also relative to the defence budget since the Russian invasion of Ukraine.¹⁶³ The defence budget of 2024 is almost double the budget of 2022, which logically increases the use of Article 346 as well.¹⁶⁴ After the Russian invasion of Ukraine, four high-value projects were initiated under Article 346.¹⁶⁵ Moreover, three projects, although long in preparation, reached final assessment on the application of Article 346 after the invasion.¹⁶⁶ Moreover, the expansion of the budget has likely reduced the weight of cost-efficiency in procurement decisions. Previously, budgetary constraints could have required the Ministry to select the lowest-cost offers. Now, with increased financial resources, procurement choices increasingly prioritize industrial policy objectives.

However, the increase should not be overstated. Through personal communication, it has become clear that although there is political support for invoking Article 346 TFEU to promote the Dutch defence industry, in practice, this is often unnecessary.¹⁶⁷ The Directive already provides specific and flexible procedures tailored to defence needs. These include exemptions through the crisis clause and deployments abroad,¹⁶⁸ which are frequently sufficient to meet operational requirements without resorting to Article 346.

Moreover, the legal and policy basis for invoking Article 346 TFEU had already been established with the *Defence Strategy* (2018), which emphasized the need to protect strategic capabilities and secure national defence industries.¹⁶⁹ The Russian invasion of Ukraine accelerated procurement but did not fundamentally alter this framework. Urgency has emerged as a possible

¹⁶³ *Kamerstukken II 2023-2024*, 36560-X, nr. 10; *Kamerstukken II 2023-2024*, 36600-X, nr. 4, p 9; Tweede Kamer der Staten-Generaal, 'Jaarverslag en slotwet Ministerie van Defensie 2023' (15 mei 2024) <<https://www.tweedekamer.nl/kamerstukken/detail?id=2024D11355&did=2024D11355>> accessed 27 June 2025, p 17; Rheinmetall Defence Nederland, 'Position Paper opschaling Defensie industrie tbv rondetafelgesprek van de vaste kamer commissie van de Tweede kamer (Position Paper, 12 juni 2024) <<https://www.tweedekamer.nl/kamerstukken/detail?id=2024Z09927&did=2024D23400>> accessed 27 June 2025, p 2.

¹⁶⁴ Zandee 2024 (n 137), p 2.

¹⁶⁵ In total, four projects can be identified whose initial publication occurred after the Russian invasion of Ukraine (*Multifunctionele ondersteunings-vaartuigen (Navy)*, *Vervanging MRAD & SHORAD (Army)*, *vervanging LC fregatten (Navy)*, and *Verwerving Amphibische Transportschepen*). These projects hold a combined estimated value of approximately EUR 7.5 billion. For all values presented as ranges, the average of the range is taken. These averages are then summed to obtain the total.

¹⁶⁶ In the following three projects, it was determined after 2022 that Article 346 TFEU is applicable, although the initial publication of the project occurred before 2022: *ESSM Block 2: Verwerving en integratie (Navy)*, *Vervanging hulpvaartuigen (Navy)*, and *Foxtrot*.

¹⁶⁷ The fact that the actual number of invocations has not risen significantly was also confirmed through personal communication with Jorm Bleijs (Utrecht, 22 May 2024).

¹⁶⁸ Directive 2009/81/EC, arts 13(d), 28(1)(c).

¹⁶⁹ *Kamerstukken II 2021-2022*, 26231, nr. 35.

ground of invocation in parliamentary debates, although there are no signs that the Ministry will also adopt this position.¹⁷⁰

3.3.2. FINANCES

Financially, the projects to which Article 346 TFEU is applied, as well as disclosed, involve major investments, often exceeding EUR 1 billion. In total, a very rough estimate of EUR 20.2 billion of procurement under Article 346 can be identified on projects in realization from 2020 until 2036 latest.¹⁷¹ These expenditures will take place during the years of realization of the projects, all starting after 2021. In 2024 specifically, around 30% of all military procurement took place under Article 346, representing a financial value of about EUR 5 billion.¹⁷² For reference, the Dutch defence budget for 2025 is approximately EUR 22 billion, of which around 44% is allocated to investments and maintenance of defence materiel through the Defence Materiel Investment Fund.¹⁷³

From an economic perspective, the systematic invocation of Article 346 TFEU has profound implications for the NLDTIB. Already in 2024, the Dutch Government had decided to shift procurement policy expressly away from purely economic efficiency to prioritizing speed, origin, and security of supply.¹⁷⁴ Direct awards to domestic firms such as Damen and Thales bolster their position. This consolidation strengthens the NLDTIB, which reduces reliance on foreign suppliers and supports the Netherlands' objective of maintaining some form of autonomy, particularly in naval systems. Nonetheless, this approach also entails drawbacks. Concentrating major defence investments among a few national champions may reduce competition and create dependencies on specific industrial actors. While strategic sovereignty is a legitimate policy objective, it may come at the cost of higher prices.¹⁷⁵

3.4. GROUNDS FOR INVOKING ARTICLE 346 TFEU

The analysis of the major Dutch defence procurement projects, laid down in Annex I, centers on the following five distinct grounds: (1) to directly award tenders to domestic firms (2) to execute a competitive procurement procedure under Article 346 TFEU, (3) to impose offset obligations on foreign suppliers, (4) to ensure secrecy and confidentiality, and (5) to ensure urgency.¹⁷⁶ All five grounds will be discussed in the stated order.

3.4.1. GROUND: DIRECT AWARDS TO SUPPORT THE NLDTIB

Article 346 TFEU is invoked to enable the direct award of contracts to Dutch companies, after an assessment by the Commissariat for Military Production. Direct awards take place without competition. For example, this occurred in the projects *Multifunctionele ondersteuningsvaartuigen*, *Vervanging Close-in Weapon System*, *ESSM Block 2*, *Vervanging hulpvaartuigen*, *Vervanging M-fregatten*, *Vervanging LC-fregatten*, *Verwerving Amfibische Transportschepen*, and *Combat Support Ship* projects. In these cases, the Ministry bypassed open tendering procedures to safeguard

¹⁷⁰ Personal communication with Jorn Bleijs (Utrecht, 22 May 2024).

¹⁷¹ See Annex I; For all values presented as ranges, the average of the range is taken. These averages are then summed to obtain the total.

¹⁷² Ministry of Defence, Internal undisclosed document on file with the author.

¹⁷³ Wet van 19 februari 2025 tot vaststelling van de begrotingsstaat van het Defensiematerieelbegrotingsfonds (K) voor het jaar 2025.

¹⁷⁴ Zandee 2024 (n 137), pp 3-4.

¹⁷⁵ Magahy & Cunha & Pyman 2010 (n 80), pp 2, 20-21.

¹⁷⁶ All sources on which the statements in this section are based, can be found in Annex I.

national technological and industrial capabilities. All these cases concern the maritime industrial capabilities of the Netherlands, which led the Netherlands to directly award these projects without a tender to Damen and Thales. The goal of these direct awards is to support the maritime industrial capabilities held by the Dutch companies.

3.4.2. GROUND: COMPETITIVE PROCUREMENT PROCEDURE UNDER ARTICLE 346 TFEU

A competitive procurement procedure is also possible under Article 346 TFEU. This procedure allows Member States to determine independently how to execute the procedure, in which it is allowed to bypass the rules of non-discrimination and transparency set by the Directive, and they remain free to set conditions. While this procedure was followed at least three times in the last few years for the projects *Onderzeeboten*, *Verbeterd Operationeel Systeem Soldaat (VOSS)*, and *155mm Precision Guided Munition (PGM) voor de PzH2000*, none of these cases were awarded to Dutch companies with the explicit, disclosed aim to support the NLDTIB. Nonetheless, it is known that when Article 346 is invoked, this does enable the government to exercise broad discretion in formulating the criteria and procedure than would be possible under the Directive. In turn, these direct awards with specific conditions, taking place under competition, can be expected to favor the national industry.

3.4.3. GROUND: OFFSET OBLIGATION

The Netherlands applies Article 346 TFEU to introduce offset obligations when foreign suppliers are selected.¹⁷⁷ This occurred in the projects *Multifunctionele ondersteuningsvaartuigen*, *Vervanging MRAD & SHORAD*, *Onderzeeboten*, *Verwerving Combat Support Ship*, *Vervanging LC fregatten*. In these cases, although the prime contractor was foreign, obligations were imposed to subcontract significant portions of production to Dutch companies. For example, in the submarine project, an Industrial Cooperation Agreement mandates that approximately EUR 1.0 billion of the total contract value must be funneled to the Dutch defence sector; as a result, ten Dutch companies will be involved in the project, as well as two knowledge institutes.¹⁷⁸ Similar to the direct awards, all of the offset cases identified concern maritime industrial capabilities.

Concerning the financial value of the offsets, the last time the Ministry reported on the value of offsets was in 2022. It was disclosed that between 2017 and 2021, the average yearly value of military offsets was EUR 313 million.¹⁷⁹

3.4.4. GROUND: SECRECY AND CONFIDENTIALITY

Articles 346(1)(a) and 346(1)(b) TFEU may be invoked to safeguard secrecy and confidentiality in defence procurement. A distinction should be made between two types: (1) the classification of an entire procurement project as secret, and (2) the confidentiality of specific content or technical requirements within a tender.

Concerning the first category, it is inherently problematic to research this category empirically, since the tenders and accompanying procedure remain secret. The Minister has made

¹⁷⁷ The Netherlands calls offsets industrial participations: see: Rijksoverheid 2025 (1) (n 158).

¹⁷⁸ *ibid*; In the Netherlands, a knowledge institute is an organization, often publicly funded, that conducts independent research and develops expertise in specific scientific, technological, or policy fields to support innovation, education, and government policymaking.

¹⁷⁹ *Kamerstukken II 2021-2022*, 26231, nr. 35.

clear in parliament that not all invocations are shared, and that it does not want to disclose how often the exemption is applied.¹⁸⁰ However, it is expected that major defence procurement projects are generally not kept secret in their entirety under Article 346 TFEU, and that these projects are disclosed and included in Annex I.

The second category, on the other hand, can be researched, as these projects as such and procedures can be disclosed. It is known that the Netherlands invokes Article 346 TFEU based on this ground. In the Netherlands, confidentiality and integrity requirements for suppliers are concretized through the ABDO regulations, which set out mandatory standards for classified defence procurements.¹⁸¹ While these ABDO regulations generally provide comprehensive safeguards for confidentiality and security in most defence procurement scenarios, in the absence of case law, it remains uncertain whether all provisions in the ABDO are in line with the Directive. The ABDO appears to contradict the principle of non-discrimination, as it imposes nationality requirements on employees and on the permanent establishments of companies.¹⁸²

On top of that, it is disclosed that Article 346 TFEU is invoked in exceptional cases to ensure secrecy and confidentiality in particularly sensitive procurement programs. This applies to the *Onderzeeboten*, *Foxtrot*, and the *Vervanging MRAD & SHORAD* projects. In the *Onderzeeboten* project, disclosure of design, operational, or technical data could compromise national security and strategic deterrence.¹⁸³ In the *Foxtrot* project, which concerns sensitive military communications equipment, security considerations equally necessitated a special procedure to avoid exposing critical information to foreign or hostile actors, although it is not yet confirmed that Article 346 will be invoked. In *Vervanging MRAD & SHORAD*, which concerns the acquisition of air defence equipment, Article 13(a) of the Directive was applied, which in practice is the codification of Article 346(1)(a) TFEU, coupled with the ability to take positive action.¹⁸⁴ Unfortunately, it was not clarified why this exemption was necessary. However, the likely reason for invoking Article 13(a) lies in the need to protect classified operational requirements, including secured wireless communications, the disclosure of which could compromise national security.

3.4.5. GROUND: URGENCY

Recently, there have been calls to invoke Article 346 TFEU in the context of urgency.¹⁸⁵ Following the procedures of the Directive is perceived as time-consuming, the opposite of what is needed since the start of the Russian invasion of Ukraine. However, as has become clear from personal communication, the Netherlands generally does not invoke Article 346 for reasons of urgency, and no such invocations could be identified.¹⁸⁶ Instead, it relies on alternative exemptions provided under the Directive that are specifically meant to be used in urgent situations. These include, most notably, (1) the exemption for defence procurement outside of the EU in case of deployment of

¹⁸⁰ Plaatsvervangend directeur-generaal beleid, 'Beslisnota bij Antwoord op vragen van de leden Eerdmans en Tuinman over aanbestedingsbureaucratie bij defensieaankopen' (17 June 2024) <<https://www.tweedekamer.nl/kamerstukken/detail?id=2024D25408&did=2024D25408>> accessed 27 June 2025.

¹⁸¹ Algemene Beveiligingseisen voor Defensieopdrachten, see: Ministry of Defence, 'Algemene Beveiligingseisen voor Defensieopdrachten 2019' (Ministerie van Defensie 2020) <<https://www.defensie.nl/downloads/beleidsnotas/2020/02/04/abdo-2019>> accessed 27 June 2025.

¹⁸² Meershoek 2023 (1) (n 137), p 411.

¹⁸³ *Kamerstukken II* 2019-2020, 34225, nr. 25, p 30-31.

¹⁸⁴ Directorate-General for Internal Market and Services 2010 (n 33), pp 4-5.

¹⁸⁵ Boston Consulting Group, 'Personele Opschalingsstrategie Defensie' (Ministerie van Defensie 2025) <<https://www.tweedekamer.nl/kamerstukken/detail?id=2025D16576&did=2025D16576>> accessed 27 June 2025, slide 30; Tweede Kamer der Staten-Generaal, 'Jaarverslag en slotwet Ministerie van Defensie 2023' (15 mei 2024) <<https://www.tweedekamer.nl/kamerstukken/detail?id=2024D11355&did=2024D11355>> accessed 27 June 2025, p 17; Rheinmetall Defence Nederland 2024 (n 163), p 2.

¹⁸⁶ Personal communication with Jorn Bleijs (Utrecht, 22 May 2024).

military forces similarly outside the EU,¹⁸⁷ and (2) the crisis exemption.¹⁸⁸ These mechanisms provide sufficient flexibility to address the procurement needs without having to resort to Article 346. While the first exemption disapplies the Directive, the second exemption allows for the application of the negotiated procedure without publication of a contract notice under Article 28 of the Directive.

The negotiated procedure without publication is preferable to Article 346 TFEU, as it includes an ex-post transparency obligation for Member States to send, when possible, a notice of the award procedure within a maximum of 48 days.¹⁸⁹ The Ministry interprets the situation in Ukraine as a crisis as meant in Article 28(1)(c),¹⁹⁰ which allows for procurement without publication for material that is sent to Ukraine.

3.5. INTERIM CONCLUSION

Chapter 3 examined how the Netherlands applies Article 346 TFEU in law and practice within its defence procurement policy, and what the grounds for invocation are. It can be concluded that the Netherlands applies Article 346 in a flexible manner within its defence procurement policy, rather than through formal legislation. While no formal legal procedure governs its invocation, the Ministry relies on a coherent policy framework, including the Security Strategy, Defence White Paper, and Defence Strategies, to define what constitutes ‘essential security interests’. In practice, the provision is invoked on several grounds: to make direct awards, to execute a competitive procurement procedure under Article 346 giving more freedom, to impose offset obligations, to protect confidentiality, and for reasons of urgency. Almost all invocations take place in the maritime sector, where firms like Damen and Thales frequently benefit from direct awards.

¹⁸⁷ Directive 2009/81/EC, art 13(d).

¹⁸⁸ *ibid*, arts 13(d), 28(1)(c).

¹⁸⁹ *ibid*, art 30(3).

¹⁹⁰ Personal communication with Jorn Bleijs (Utrecht, 22 May 2024).

CHAPTER 4. GERMANY

Chapter 4 analyzes similarly to chapter 3 first in section 4.1. how the German government defines 'essential security interests'. Then, in section 4.2., the procedures established for invoking Article 346 TFEU are analyzed; section 4.3. analyzes the invocations of Article 346, and section 4.4. discusses the grounds for invocation.

4.1. ESSENTIAL SECURITY INTERESTS

In Germany, the identification of 'essential security interests' under Article 346(1)(b) TFEU is marked by the *Zeitenwende* political change. The security interests are articulated in three key documents, all published after the *Zeitenwende*: the *National Security Strategy* (2023),¹⁹¹ the *Defence Policy Guidelines* (2023),¹⁹² and the *National Security and Defence Industry Strategy* (2023).¹⁹³ Together, these documents establish a framework of Germany's security policy. Moreover, Chancellor Merz also expressed the new German government's geopolitical efforts.

The National Security Strategy (2023) articulates a broad security doctrine. The government introduces three dimensions of a secure society: a robust, resilient, and sustainable society.¹⁹⁴ It presents a wide range of threats: conventional military aggression, cyberattacks, disinformation campaigns, energy dependency, the weaponization of supply chains, and hybrid warfare.¹⁹⁵ Russia's war against Ukraine is explicitly identified as the defining threat to the European security order. Accordingly, the strategy views the protection of territorial integrity, democratic institutions, and critical infrastructures, not only in the physical domain but also in the cyber and information domains, as security priorities. Germany wants to decrease dependencies on autocratic regimes and expand both civil and military preparedness for crisis and conflict.¹⁹⁶ The *National Security Strategy* (2023) emphasizes that the boundaries between internal and external security are fading, and that a society-wide response to the threats is necessary.¹⁹⁷

The Defence Policy Guidelines (2023) further shape the priorities of the Bundeswehr. The Guidelines identify national and collective defence as the Bundeswehr's number 1 core task.¹⁹⁸ They start with the fact that the strengthening of Germany's armed forces is necessary, given the new geopolitical order and Germany's role as an industrial center in Europe. In total, the armed forces have five core tasks; most importantly, these include defending the country and fulfilling its alliance obligations.¹⁹⁹ Fulfilling these tasks demands the Bundeswehr's ability to deter, fight, and sustain operations across multiple domains, both for Germany's national security and in the context of NATO operations.²⁰⁰ At the end, the Guidelines define seven principles for a robust Bundeswehr: personnel strength, a coherent structure at all levels, strong and (importantly) 'timely'

¹⁹¹ Federal Government of Germany, *National Security Strategy: Robust. Resilient. Sustainable. Integrated Security for Germany* (Federal Foreign Office 2023).

¹⁹² Federal Ministry of Defence, *Defence Policy Guidelines 2023* (Federal Ministry of Defence 2023).

¹⁹³ Federal Ministry of Defence, *National Security and Defence Industry Strategy* (Federal Ministry of Defence 2023).

¹⁹⁴ Federal Government of Germany 2023 (n 191), pp 10-17.

¹⁹⁵ *ibid*, pp 22-26.

¹⁹⁶ *ibid*, pp 55-56.

¹⁹⁷ *ibid*, p 30.

¹⁹⁸ Federal Ministry of Defence 2023 (1) (n 192), p 17.

¹⁹⁹ *ibid*, pp 17-19.

²⁰⁰ *ibid*, p 31.

infrastructure, a much more generous budget than before, readiness to counter climate change, and an efficient armaments and procurement policy.²⁰¹

The National Security and Defence Industry Strategy (2023) links the procurement process to the German Defence Technological and Industrial Base (GDTIB). It defines Germany's security and defence industry as a sector of both national and European strategic interest.²⁰² The strategy identifies a core list of key technologies as essential to national security: these include naval shipbuilding, protected vehicles, secure IT and communication systems, sensors, artificial intelligence, and electronic warfare.²⁰³ These technologies must be available domestically. Moreover, the Strategy defines key technologies that must be available in close European, or international (including NATO) partnership, of which safe supply and availability are essential in the national security interest.²⁰⁴ These include quantum technologies, missiles and missile defence, space technologies, ammunition, unmanned systems, small arms, IT hardware, unprotected vehicles, and aircraft. The strategy emphasizes not only the European defence industry but also the EU's role as a defence partner in the defence industry and defence equipment.

Building on this strategic framework, the Government's *Strategy Paper on Strengthening the Security and Defence Industry (2020)* translates these broad priorities into measures to strengthen the GDTIB.²⁰⁵ However, the document does not say anything explicitly about the invocation of Article 346 TFEU to advance these security interests. The only point made in this regard is that an examination of offset opportunities needs to be made when procurement takes place outside of EU procurement law, which could happen through an invocation of Article 346.²⁰⁶ Moreover, the document stresses the importance of maintaining long-term technological leadership, including the involvement of SMEs.

Recently appointed Chancellor Merz takes a more hawkish stance in international politics than his predecessor on the necessity to take security measures. Merz, in his first major budget address, stated that the Russian invasion of Ukraine necessitated an exemption for all defence outlays above 1 percent of GDP from the debt brake, and the constitution was amended for this reason.²⁰⁷ In his very first policy statement to the Bundestag, Merz declared that Germany aims to lead the strongest conventional armed forces in Europe, for which the financial resources have to be provided.²⁰⁸

The overarching essential security interests emerging from these documents reveal a need for broad preparedness by the Bundeswehr. The following four broad interests could be composed:

1. the capability to act autonomously both inside and outside Germany in critical defence scenarios;

²⁰¹ *ibid*, pp 26-31.

²⁰² Federal Ministry of Defence 2023 (2) (n 193), pp 5-7.

²⁰³ *ibid*, pp 8-14.

²⁰⁴ *ibid*, pp 8-9.

²⁰⁵ Die Bundesregierung, 'Strategy Paper of the Federal Government on Strengthening the Security and Defence Industry' (Die Bundesregierung, 2020) <https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&opi=89978449&url=https://www.bmwk.de/Redaktion/DE/Downloads/S-T/strategiepapier-staerkung-sicherits-und-verteidigungsindustrie-en.pdf%3F__blob%3DpublicationFile%26v%3D4&ved=2ahUKewjw7JXj24COAxV8-QIHHZldEgEQFnoECAkQAQ&usq=AOvVaw2VqbfkVbsXUCPI-WOHj9Te> accessed 27 June 2025.

²⁰⁶ Federal Ministry of Defence 2023 (2) (n 193), p 12.

²⁰⁷ Friedrich Merz, 'Germany's Merz vows to build Europe's strongest army' Politico' (Berlin, 14 May 2025) <<https://www.politico.eu/article/friedrich-merz-germany-bundestag-europe-conventional-army/>> accessed 27 June 2025.

²⁰⁸ Federal Government of Germany, 'First government statement on 14 May 2025' (*The Federal Government*, 14 May 2025) <<https://www.bundesregierung.de/breg-en/news/first-government-statement-chancellor-merz-2347710>> accessed 27 June 2025.

2. the autonomy and resilience of the GDTIB, especially in its so-called key technologies;
3. protection against hybrid, digital threats, and socio-economic threats;
4. the ability to execute all NATO obligations.

4.1.1. GERMAN DEFENCE TECHNOLOGICAL AND INDUSTRIAL BASE

The GDTIB is a significant economic sector, directly employing around 105.000 individuals. The sector generates an economic output of around EUR 31.0 billion annually.²⁰⁹ The industry comprises many different enterprises. SMEs constitute a significant portion of the sector, often specializing in niche areas and contributing to the innovation and flexibility of the defence supply chain. Key players in the German defence industry include:

- Rheinmetall AG: Rheinmetall is a leading defence contractor with a wide variety of products and specializes in land military equipment. In 2023, Rheinmetall had a turnover of EUR 7.2 billion and employed over 31000 individuals.²¹⁰
- Hensoldt AG: Hensoldt is a prominent defence electronics company focusing on sensor technologies, including radar and optronics. In 2023, Hensoldt had a turnover of EUR 1.8 billion.²¹¹
- ThyssenKrupp Marine Systems: ThyssenKrupp specializes in naval shipbuilding, including submarines and surface vessels. In 2024, TKMS had a turnover of EUR 2.1 billion.²¹²

Beyond these major entities, the German defence industry is characterized by a large network of SMEs, which are integral to the supply chain. These SMEs contribute significantly to innovation and the development of specialized components and systems, reinforcing the industry's adaptability and technological advancement. The *Bundesverband der Deutschen Sicherheits- und Verteidigungsindustrie* is the primary association representing the interests of Germany's defence industry.²¹³ The organization advocates for the industry's competitiveness and sustainability.

Additionally, the German defence industry is also strengthened by the German automotive industry, which has become a vital partner to defence industry companies. The three key players of the German defence industry listed above have connections to the car industry: Rheinmetall AG entered into a joint venture with MAN Truck & Bus to manufacture logistics vehicles.²¹⁴ Thyssenkrupp Marine Systems operates under the parent group Thyssenkrupp AG, which also holds Thyssenkrupp Automotive Technology,²¹⁵ and Hensoldt AG offered employment to nearly two hundred laid off employees from car manufactures Continental and Bosch as recently as January

²⁰⁹ Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Klimaschutz, 'Sicherheits- und Verteidigungsindustrie' (*BMWK*, 4 December 2024) <<https://www.bmwk.de/Redaktion/DE/Artikel/Branchenfokus/Industrie/branchenfokus-sicherheits-und-verteidigungsindustrie.html>> accessed 27 June 2025.

²¹⁰ Rheinmetall AG, 'Rheinmetall is on track for success: another all-time earnings high, new record order backlog' (Media Release, *Rheinmetall*, 14 March 2024) <<https://ir.rheinmetall.com/investor-relations/news/financial-reports/>> accessed 27 June 2025.

²¹¹ Hensoldt AG, 'Annual Report of Hensoldt AG 2024' (2024) <<https://annualreport.hensoldt.net/en/downloads/>> accessed 27 June 2025.

²¹² Thyssenkrupp, 'Thyssenkrupp Marine Systems continue sits course of strong growth in business year 2023/2024' (Media Release, *Thyssenkrupp* 2024) <https://d2zo35mdb530wx.cloudfront.net/_binary/UCPhthyssenkruppMarineSystems/82b01348-0ad4-4880-b76b-fb959a5f18dd/Press-release---tkMS-business-year-23-24.pdf> accessed 27 June 2025.

²¹³ BDSV, see: <<https://www.bdsv.eu/presentation.html>>.

²¹⁴ Rheinmetall AG, 'Rheinmetall MAN Military Vehicles GmbH: Professional military logistics excellence' (*Rheinmetall*) <<https://www.rheinmetall.com/en/company/subsidiaries/rheinmetall-man-military-vehicles/about-us>> accessed 27 June 2025.

²¹⁵ Thyssenkrupp AG, 'Automotive Technology' (*Thyssenkrupp AG*, 2025) <<https://www.thyssenkrupp.com/en/company/corporate-structure/automotive-technology>> accessed 27 June 2025.

2025.²¹⁶ In the future, Germany could leverage its automotive industry as a source to advance and grow the GDTIB. Already, Germany is exploring the transformation of automotive manufacturing facilities for defence production.²¹⁷

4.2. LEGAL AND ADMINISTRATIVE PROCEDURE OF INVOKING ARTICLE 346 TFEU

In Germany, the legal framework for invoking Article 346 TFEU is found in section 107(2) and 117 *Gesetz gegen Wettbewerbsbeschränkungen* (GWB).²¹⁸ Section 107(2) GWB transposes Article 346(1)(b) TFEU, and section 117 GWB transposes Article 346(1)(a) TFEU into the German legal system.²¹⁹

Since its 2020 amendment, section 107(2) GWB explicitly declares that contracts concerning certain key technologies are presumed to touch upon essential security interests within the meaning of Article 346 TFEU.²²⁰ This presumption lowers the evidentiary burden for the exemption and was explicitly included to make it easier to invoke Article 346. Moreover, there have been calls in parliament to widen section 107(2) further to clarify the vague legal terms in section 107 (2) GWB in a new paragraph to create a broader interpretation of the exemption and thus a less restrictive application of Article 346.²²¹ A broader interpretation would enable the BAANBw, the procurement agency of Germany, to utilize Article 346 more easily when national security concerns are affected. Transposing Article 346 directly into German national law in a specific way thereby signals the legislature's intent to apply Article 346. Building upon this law, key technologies are defined in published documents. Specifically, the German *Strategy on Strengthening the Security and Defence Industry*²²² and the *National Security and Defence Industry Strategy*²²³ designate the key technologies,²²⁴ thereby justifying their exclusion from open tendering.

Section 117 GWB provides an exemption in procurement procedures that involve defence or security aspects. The section states that contracts to which Article 346(1)(a) TFEU is applicable are excluded from the procurement regime. Moreover, the section includes the exemptions of Article 12 in the Directive.

²¹⁶ Laura Alviz and Monica Raymunt, 'Hensoldt Offers to Take Over Continental, Bosch Workers' (*Bloomberg*, 31 January 2025) <<https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2025-01-31/hensoldt-offers-to-take-over-continental-s-unwanted-auto-workers>> accessed 27 June 2025.

²¹⁷ Linus Höller, 'Defense companies jack up Germany's auto industry to make weapons fast' (*Defense News*, 10 March 2025) <<https://www.defensenews.com/global/europe/2025/03/10/defense-companies-jack-up-germanys-auto-industry-to-make-weapons-fast/>> accessed 27 June 2025; Defence Industry Europe, 'Germany Considers Converting Automotive Factories to Defence Production' (*Defence Industry Europe*, 14 March 2025) <<https://defence-industry.eu/germany-considers-converting-automotive-factories-to-defence-production/>> accessed 27 June 2025.

²¹⁸ Gesetz gegen Wettbewerbsbeschränkungen 1957.

²¹⁹ Pascal Friton and Florian Wolf, 'The Protection of "Key Defence and Security Technology" Under the Revised German Public Procurement Law and Its Compatibility with Article 346 TFEU' (2020) *Public Procurement Law Review* 89.

²²⁰ *ibid.*, 89-91, 94-95; Wissenschaftliche Dienste, 'Die Vergabe von Rettungsdienstleistungen nach § 107 GWB: Einzelfragen' (Deutscher Bundestag 2019).

²²¹ Friedrich Merz, Alexander Dobrindt und Fraktion, 'Entschließungsantrag der Fraktion der CDU/CSU zu der dritten Beratung des Gesetzentwurfs der Fraktionen SPD, BÜNDNIS 90/DIE GRÜNEN und FDP: Entwurf eines Gesetzes zur Beschleunigung von Beschaffungsmaßnahmen für die Bundeswehr (Bundeswehrbeschaffungsbeschleunigungsgesetz: BwBBG)' (Drucksache 20/2624, 6 July 2022) <<https://dserver.bundestag.de/btd/20/026/2002624.pdf>> accessed 27 June 2025.

²²² Die bundesregierung 2020 (n 205), p 3.

²²³ Federal Ministry of Defence 2023 (2) (n 193), pp 8-9.

²²⁴ As discussed in section 3.1., domestically, these include naval shipbuilding, protected vehicles, secure IT and communication systems, sensors, artificial intelligence, and electronic warfare.

Administratively, the process of invoking Article 346 TFEU is largely internal to the Federal Government. The BAAINBw evaluates the applicability of Article 346 on a case-by-case basis.²²⁵ Although the government declared some technologies as essential to sovereignty with the inclusion of 'key industries' in § 107(2) GWB, each procurement decision must be individually justified.²²⁶ Moreover, German courts retain the power to scrutinize each invocation rigorously. The BAAINBw determines whether the disapplication of EU procurement law is necessary and proportionate to protect essential security interests. It is not published at what hierarchical level the decision to invoke Article 346 is made. However, it has become clear from conversations that such a decision is prepared by a small group of leading people in the BAAINBw and must be approved by the Minister.²²⁷

In addition to the administrative framework, parliamentary oversight plays an important role. According to section 54(3) of the *Bundshaushaltsordnung*,²²⁸ any procurement contract exceeding EUR 25 million must receive prior approval from the Budget Committee of the Bundestag.²²⁹ This obligation for parliamentary approval logically also includes the right of the Bundestag to be formally informed of the grounds of the invocation and the financial cost.

4.3. INVOCATIONS OF ARTICLE 346 TFEU

Germany has traditionally invoked Article 346 TFEU in a highly protective and secretive manner, without any disclosure of the invocations of Article 346. For this research, I have had extensive contact with four academics and professionals in German defence procurement,²³⁰ none of whom could say anything definite about the number of applications of Article 346 by the BAAINBw. This impairs the possibilities for research of the German policies in this area of European law. No extensive list of invocations can be compiled, no officially disclosed and recognized grounds for invocation can be studied, and even courts do not disclose many of the facts in published cases. However, through various ways, which are explained in the methodology of this research, this thesis intends to describe and scrutinize the invocations of Article 346 by Germany meticulously. While complete precision is unattainable, this study seeks to identify and analyze broader patterns and tendencies in Germany's invocation practice. Since there appears to be a divide in policy on Article 346 before and after the Russian invasion of Ukraine, this section will be subdivided into two subsections discussing these two time periods separately.

²²⁵ Federal Office of Bundeswehr Equipment, Information Technology and In-Service Support (BAAINBw), 'The Bundeswehr as a Customer' (2024) <<https://www.bundeswehr.de/resource/blob/954970/0dc84ef297a18eb6a42225abe73342c7/broschuere-auftraggeber-bundeswehr-en-data.pdf>> accessed 27 June 2025.

²²⁶ Bundestag, 'Antwort der Bundesregierung auf die Kleine Anfrage der Fraktion der CDU/CSU: Munition in der Bundeswehr: Aktueller Sachstand, Bedarfe und Planungen' (Drucksache 20/4509, 14 November 2022) <<https://dserver.bundestag.de/btd/20/045/2004509.pdf>> accessed 27 June 2025; Bundestag, 'Antwort der Bundesregierung auf die Kleine Anfrage der Fraktion der CDU/CSU: Zur Zukunft der deutschen Rüstungs- und Verteidigungsfähigkeit' (Drucksache 20/11868, 10 June 2024) <<https://dserver.bundestag.de/btd/20/118/2011868.pdf>> accessed 27 June 2025, p 2.

²²⁷ Personal communication with Marc Pauka (videocall, 2 May 2025); Personal communication with Marc Greitens (videocall, 5 May 2025).

²²⁸ Bundshaushaltsordnung 1969.

²²⁹ Wissenschaftliche Dienste 2024 (n 32).

²³⁰ See the bibliography for the list of people contacted.

4.3.1. PRE-2022 INVOCATIONS

Before the Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2022, it seems that the German approach to invoking Article 346 TFEU was extremely strict and highly conservative.²³¹ On top of that, between 2019 and early 2022, Germany published the highest number of contract award notices under the Directive of all EU member states, being 3106.²³² It appears that only a handful of invocations of Article 346 between 2019 and early 2022 took place.²³³ One possible reason for this cautious approach is Germany's standing record of frequent public procurement review proceedings. In 2022, for instance, 702 applications for review were submitted to the public procurement chambers (*Vergabekammern*), and in 2021, this number was even higher, with 865 applications.²³⁴ This consistent level of judicial scrutiny likely contributed to the reluctance of German authorities to invoke Article 346. Not only has there been a pattern of judicial applications, but during those proceedings, German courts also tended to interpret the exemption under Article 346 narrowly. This is a trend that was publicly illustrated in three cases decided between 2019 and 2021.

In *VK 2-87/20* from November 2020, the Federal Public Procurement Chamber (*Vergabekammern des Bundes*) dealt with a procurement concerning the manufacture and delivery of military vessels.²³⁵ The applicant, a foreign supplier whose identity is undisclosed, was rejected in his bid for the contract by the German government, and the rejection was based on Article 346 TFEU. The appeal was dismissed, and the invocation of Article 346 was initially judged to be lawful, which meant that the applicant's rejection was lawful. The procurement concerned military support ships, specially modified for military purposes.²³⁶ The ground for invoking Article 346 was the preservation of the GDTIB in shipbuilding, which the German Government had classified as a national key defence technology.²³⁷ Allowing a competitive EU-wide tender could jeopardize the award of the contract to the German industry.²³⁸ Concerning necessity and proportionality, the Chamber states that a procurement procedure under the Directive, including national production obligations through security of supply obligations, would not be sufficient, because it would expose the process to competition from EU (foreign) shipyards, thereby threatening the national industrial base.

The applicant subsequently appealed to the Düsseldorf Higher Regional Court (*Oberlandesgericht Vergabesenat*) in the case *VII-Verg 51/20* from August 2021.²³⁹ Although the application was withdrawn before a final judgment on the merits was delivered, the court nonetheless issued a reasoned decision, which included an analysis of Article 346 TFEU. The court recognized that Member States have broad discretion to determine the essential security interests, although the discretion is not absolute.²⁴⁰ The court also reiterated that Article 346 is only applicable

²³¹ Martin Trybus and Pascal Friton, 'Germany rearmed: The impact of the Ukraine War on German defence procurement law and policy' (2023) 32 *Public Procurement Law Review* 1, pp 5-6; Marc Pauka, "'Zeitenwende" in Public Procurement Law: Security Interests, Military Procurement, and the Ukraine War' (2024) 19 *European Procurement & Public Private Partnership Law Review* 153, p 154; Personal communication with Marc Pauka (videocall, 2 May 2025); Personal communication with Marc Greitens (videocall, 5 May 2025).

²³² Loannides 2020 (n 5), p 89-90.

²³³ Personal communication with Marc Pauka (videocall, 2 May 2025).

²³⁴ Christopher Wolters and Pascal Friton, 'Snapshot: Public Procurement Review Proceedings in Germany' (*Lexology*, 18 June 2024) <<https://www.lexology.com/library/detail.aspx?g=78f7b6d4-ee44-4306-9f9c-fb08d9d4573d>> accessed 27 June 2025; Paolina Ilieva, 'Legal 500 Country Comparative Guides 2025: Germany Public Procurement' (*Legal 500* 2025) <<https://www.legal500.com/guides/chapter/germany-public-procurement/>> accessed 27 June 2025, p 10.

²³⁵ *VK 2-87/20* [2020] Vergabekammer des Bundes (Bundeskartellamt publication).

²³⁶ *ibid*, pp 1-9.

²³⁷ *ibid*, pp 15-16.

²³⁸ *ibid*, p 18.

²³⁹ *VII-Verg 51/20* [2021] Oberlandesgericht Düsseldorf (OpenJur publication).

²⁴⁰ *ibid*, paras 30-32.

to equipment on the 1958 Arms List.²⁴¹ However, concerning proportionality and necessity, the court prescribes a very strict assessment. The court stresses that Article 346 limits the possible applications of Article 346 to the utmost critical contracts.²⁴² According to the court, those can be, for example, contracts with a high strategic value, particular confidentiality, or high demands on the security of supply. The court also rejected the use of solely general industrial strategy arguments and stated that general arguments imply that the motive is largely economic and not genuinely related to military capability.²⁴³ Lastly, the court also criticized reliance on section 107(2) GWB and states that the provision cannot be used in a stand-alone manner, as only Article 346 can provide the basis for the derogation. The legislature, when codifying 107(2) GWB, included the section as an interpretive mechanism to explain how Article 346 can apply in Germany.²⁴⁴ The classification of certain technologies as key technologies alone, thus is not sufficient to invoke 346, unless this is supported by a specific justification.

Similarly, in *VK 2-91/20* from December 2020,²⁴⁵ the Federal Public Procurement Chamber dealt with a procurement concerning the repair and maintenance capacities of national shipyards. In this case, the contracting authority cancelled a contract with a Polish shipyard in order to award the contract to a German firm. The Polish shipyard appealed the decision, and the appeal was successful. While the legality of the cancellation of the contract was discussed on the basis of § 37(1)(2) German Defence and Security Procurement Regulation,²⁴⁶ Article 346 TFEU was discussed as the expected legal basis for a subsequent direct award to a German shipyard.²⁴⁷ In this context, the judgment raises doubts about its applicability of Article 346. Firstly, the court states that to invoke Article 346(1)(b) TFEU, the object of the procurement must fall under the 1958 Arms List, and it expresses doubt about whether routine maintenance of a non-combat support ship qualifies.²⁴⁸ Moreover, the court also states that there was no demonstrated threat to national security. In this context, the government refers to a 2020 strategy paper, but the court finds this insufficient and says that referring to an industrial strategy does not automatically allow the invocation of Article 346, but is merely a relevant factor.²⁴⁹ Lastly, the court states that the contract's low value (several million in value) does not show systemic relevance.²⁵⁰

Taken together, the decisions illustrate that prior to the Russian invasion of Ukraine, German procurement courts applied Article 346 TFEU narrowly and with rigorous scrutiny. Although it is hard to prove, the demands imposed by German courts on contracting authorities may have even exceeded those established by the Court. The rigorous scrutiny from the courts may, however, also have an unintended side effect: it likely incentivizes the BAANBw to rely more heavily on other exemptions under EU law or under the Directive, which are subject to less judicial resistance and may appear more legally secure. This hypothesis is further supported by the fact that, as illustrated in section 1.1, Germany awards less than 2.0% of its procurement spending through competitively tendered contracts.

In this context, however, it is also important to note that it could paradoxically also be beneficial for countries with a strong and competitive defence industry to engage in open procedures

²⁴¹ *ibid*, para 11.

²⁴² *ibid*, paras 32-33.

²⁴³ *ibid*, paras 34-35.

²⁴⁴ *ibid*, paras 38-41.

²⁴⁵ *VK 2-91/20* [2020] Vergabekammer des Bundes (Bundeskartellamt publication).

²⁴⁶ Verteidigungsvergabeverordnung 2012, section 37(1)(2)

²⁴⁷ *ibid*, p 7.

²⁴⁸ *ibid*, p 11.

²⁴⁹ *ibid*, pp 11-12.

²⁵⁰ *ibid*, p 5.

and make other countries engage in open procedures.²⁵¹ For Member States such as Germany or France, whose defence sectors are technologically advanced and economically efficient, their industries are well-positioned to win tenders on the basis of quality and price. This is supported by data showing that while on average 84 percent of contracts are awarded to national suppliers, for Germany and France, this is highest with 98% and 97% respectively between the transposition of the Directive and July 2015.²⁵² When other countries procure equipment openly and non-discriminatory, this can result in the domination of big industries beyond their borders, which in turn reinforces the strategic position of the big industries in the EDTIB. Therefore, it is expected that countries like Germany and France, in general, are more positive towards the idea of procuring competitively in the European market.

4.3.2. POST-2022 INVOCATIONS

Since the Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2022, Germany has increasingly relied on Article 346 TFEU to exempt defence procurements from EU public procurement rules. First, the important case *Verg 22/23* will be discussed. Beyond the judiciary, the political and administrative practice will be discussed.

In *Verg 22/23* of December 2023, the Higher Regional Court showed signs of adapting its strict approach.²⁵³ The case concerns the Ministry's procurement of tactical communication systems. Initially tendered through a European procedure in 2021, the procedure was changed after the Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2022. In reaction to the changed security environment, Germany decided to directly award a contract for secure communication devices to a national supplier without EU-wide competition. This decision was justified by invoking § 107(2) GWB in conjunction with Article 346 TFEU, arguing the protection of essential security interests.²⁵⁴ Specifically, a high degree of confidentiality was necessary, which could not be ensured under the Directive.²⁵⁵

The procurement concerned military electronic material, thus falling within the material scope of the 1958 Arms List referenced by Article 346(2) TFEU.²⁵⁶ However, the discussion of the proportionality and necessity requirements proved most consequential. The court accepted that the radical deterioration of security conditions following Russia's aggression justified the abandonment of open procurement procedures.²⁵⁷ This caused the Bundeswehr to urgently procure secure, interoperable, and deployment-ready tactical communication systems to meet new alliance defence obligations.²⁵⁸ It is explicitly stated that speed was necessary in this case.²⁵⁹ By discussing this point, the Court recognizes that urgency might be a potential legal ground to invoke Article 346. Moreover, the Regional Court also recognizes that open competition would have required the disclosure of technical specifications and that even minimal disclosure would entail the risk of leaked sensitive information about the German military capabilities.²⁶⁰

Consequently, the court found that the exemption was properly applied. With this case, the judiciary broadened the possibilities for Germany to invoke Article 346 TFEU. The case marks a clear shift in German procurement practice, as Germany, which is traditionally cautious in invoking

²⁵¹ Meershoek 2023 (3) (n 2), pp 213-214.

²⁵² Masson & Martin 2025 (n 15), p 35.

²⁵³ *VII-Verg 22/23* [2023] Oberlandesgericht Düsseldorf (Justizportal Nordrhein-Westfalen publication).

²⁵⁴ *ibid*, paras 1-39.

²⁵⁵ *ibid*, para 112.

²⁵⁶ *ibid*, paras 98-101.

²⁵⁷ *ibid*, paras 112, 115.

²⁵⁸ *ibid*, para 115.

²⁵⁹ *ibid*, paras 10-16.

²⁶⁰ *ibid*, paras 112-116.

Article 346 TFEU, reacted quickly to the new geopolitical realities, recognizing external threats as reasons to invoke Article 346, as well as urgency reasons.²⁶¹

Beyond the judiciary, the political and administrative practice shows an increase in the use of Article 346 TFEU. Through personal communication,²⁶² as well as statements made in parliamentary proceedings,²⁶³ it seems evident that the German government applies Article 346 more often than before. A professional in the field, too, highlighted that invocations of Article 346 have intensified since 2022.²⁶⁴ In addition to those statements, in 2022, the German Bundestag adopted the German Armed Forces Procurement Acceleration Act,²⁶⁵ a German law aimed at accelerating military procurement procedures in response to Russia's invasion of Ukraine, partly by limiting judicial review and other means.²⁶⁶ Experts who shared their opinion during public hearings for the law also reiterated the desire for a broader application of Article 346.²⁶⁷ Together, all these political actions show an environment in which broader and more flexible use of Article 346 is endorsed.

Additionally, multiple political actions have been taken recently aimed at rebuilding the Bundeswehr in connection to loosening EU defence procurement law. The recent coalition agreement of 2025 stressed the need to strengthen the German and European security and defence industries.²⁶⁸ Although this agreement does not mention Article 346 TFEU explicitly, it implies a heightened desire to procure outside EU defence procurement law to award contracts directly to the DTIBB. Furthermore, the new government plans to simplify procurement procedures for the Bundeswehr through new legislative initiatives.²⁶⁹ On top of that, in January 2025, the largest fraction in the Bundestag, CDU/CSU, released a paper in which it explains how it plans to widen the scope of Article 346, both nationally by reforming 107(2) GWB, and European-wide by proposing a revision of the 1958 Arms List.²⁷⁰

²⁶¹ This analysis is also shared by: Robert Glawe and Julia Radau, 'A turning point in jurisprudence too? Case law on Article 346(1)(b) TFEU and the Command Radio Equipment Decision' [2024] *VergabeR* 654; Pauka 2024 (1) (n 231). Moreover, a parallel could be drawn with post-9/11 events, see: Marc Pauka, '„Zeitenwende“ und „Kriegstüchtigkeit“ im Vergaberecht: Teil 1' [2024] *VergabeR* 605, pp 607-608. In this article, Marc Pauka argues that following the terrorist attacks of 9/11, Germany more extensively relied on security exemptions to bypass ordinary procurement procedures. German courts became more lenient and allowed procurement exemptions when the 9/11 events were referred to as necessity grounds.

²⁶² Personal communication with Marc Pauka (videocall, 2 May 2025); Personal communication with Marc Greitens (videocall, 5 May 2025).

²⁶³ Bundestag, 'Antwort der Bundesregierung auf die Kleine Anfrage der Abgeordneten Dr. Marcus Faber, Alexander Müller, Frank Schäffler, weiterer Abgeordneter und der Fraktion der FDP' (Drucksache 20/11754, 17 April 2024) <<https://dserver.bundestag.de/btd/20/117/2011754.pdf>> accessed 27 June 2025, pp 4-5; Bundestag, 'Zu der dritten Beratung des Gesetzentwurfs der Fraktionen SPD, Bündnis 90/Die Grünen und FDP' (Drucksache 20/2624, 23 June 2022) <<https://dserver.bundestag.de/btd/20/026/2002624.pdf>> accessed 27 June 2025.

²⁶⁴ Personal communication with Roland Haag (email, 13 May 2025).

²⁶⁵ Bundeswehrbeschaffungsbeschleunigungsgesetz 2022.

²⁶⁶ Ingrid Reichling and Christopher Montgomery Vollert, 'The Wind of Change Called Zeitenwende: Quo Vadis in Accelerated Defence Procurement, Germany?' (2023) *European Procurement & Public Private Partnership Law Review* 150.

²⁶⁷ Matthias Wachter, 'Stellungnahme zur öffentlichen Anhörung zum Entwurf eines Gesetzes zur Beschleunigung von Beschaffungsmaßnahmen für die Bundeswehr' (Bundestag, 1 July 2022); Reinhard Dr Atzpodien, 'Stellungnahme zur öffentlichen Anhörung zum Entwurf eines Gesetzes zur Beschleunigung von Beschaffungsmaßnahmen für die Bundeswehr' (Bundestag, 1 July 2022); Michael Essig, 'Stellungnahme zur öffentlichen Anhörung zum Entwurf eines Gesetzes zur Beschleunigung von Beschaffungsmaßnahmen für die Bundeswehr' (Bundestag, 1 July 2022).

²⁶⁸ CDU, CSU und SPD, 'Verantwortung für Deutschland: Koalitionsvertrag zwischen CDU, CSU und SPD' (Berlin, 2025) <https://www.spd.de/fileadmin/Dokumente/Koalitionsvertrag2025_bf.pdf> accessed 27 June 2025, pp 131-132.

²⁶⁹ *ibid*, p 131.

²⁷⁰ CDU/CSU-Fraktion im Deutschen Bundestag, 'Reformplan für das Beschaffungswesen der Bundeswehr bis 2029' (Positionspapier, 28 January 2025) <<https://www.cdusu.de/sites/default/files/2025-01/PP%20Beschaffungswesen.pdf>> accessed 27 June 2025, p 16.

4.4. GROUNDS FOR INVOKING ARTICLE 346 TFEU

In this section, it is analyzed what the German grounds are for invoking Article 346 TFEU. This analysis is grounded in political statements, judicial cases discussed above, and three invocations of Article 346 discussed in Annex II.²⁷¹ The following grounds will be discussed in identical order: (1) direct awards, (2) secrecy and confidentiality, and (3) urgency. It is unclear whether Germany, similar to the Netherlands, has applied Article 346 to competitively procure equipment under a procedure exempted from EU law.

4.4.1. GROUND: DIRECT AWARDS TO SUPPORT THE GDTIB

One of the main grounds for invoking Article 346 TFEU by the German government likely concerns directly awarding contracts to German defence companies. This ground is linked to Article 346(1)(b) TFEU and its foundation in Germany is section 107 GWB. Section 107 GWB explicitly allows for the application of Article 346 when key technologies are involved. This implies that the exemption is primarily used to support the German industry through direct awards to German contractors.

Two invocations have been identified that were likely grounded in the industrial goal of strengthening the GDTIB. The procurement of 62 *H145M helicopters* for the Bundeswehr, valued at USD 2,3 billion, involved a direct award to Airbus. Airbus produces these helicopters in Donauwörth, Germany, and on top of that, Airbus is a key player in the German-French aerospace sector. Similarly, for the acquisition of *155mm SMART ammunition*, the massive contract worth EUR 8.5 billion benefits Rheinmetall, a cornerstone of the German defence industry.

The recurring invocations of Article 346 TFEU based on this ground are also substantiated through case law. In *VK 2-87/20* and *VII-Verg 51/20*,²⁷² the German government had invoked Article 346 specifically to protect the German shipbuilding industry, which dealt with a procurement concerning the construction of naval support ships. Here, Article 346 was invoked explicitly to protect the domestic shipbuilding industry, which the German government had previously recognized as a key technology. A similar ground was invoked in the case *VK 2-91/20*,²⁷³ in which the German government canceled a contract with a Polish shipyard to re-award the contract to a German shipyard to protect the GDTIB.

4.4.2. GROUND: OFFSETS

While there are no identified invocations to realize offsets, the new government coalition agreement does state that offset opportunities should be utilized.²⁷⁴ Unfortunately, due to a lack of data on this ground, no assessment can be made.

4.4.3. GROUND: SECRECY AND CONFIDENTIALITY

Similar to the discussion with the Netherlands, a distinction is made between: (1) the classification of an entire procurement project as secret, and (2) the restriction of access to specific content or technical requirements within a tender due to confidentiality reasons.

²⁷¹ The sources for these three projects can be found in Annex II.

²⁷² *VK 2-87/20* [2020] (n 235); *VII-Verg 51/20* [2021] (n 239).

²⁷³ *VK 2-91/20* [2020] (n 245).

²⁷⁴ CDU, CSU and SPD, 'Verantwortung für Deutschland: Koalitionsvertrag zwischen CDU, CSU und SPD' (Berlin, 2025) <https://www.spd.de/fileadmin/Dokumente/Koalitionsvertrag2025_bf.pdf> accessed 27 June 2025, pp 131-132.

While it is inherently difficult to draw conclusions on category 1, there are signs that the German government applies Article 346 TFEU to keep procurements secret from external parties outside the government. Secrecy remains a characteristic feature of German procurement procedures. German authorities consistently argue that procurement processes involving sensitive defence projects risk exposing classified information and therefore, in principle, do not disclose any information about any of their invocations of Article 346.²⁷⁵ According to the German government, disclosing any technical specifications could compromise national security and military effectiveness.

Moreover, category 2 is also likely applied by Germany. The *Verg 22/23* case illustrates this point. In this case, the German court recognized that disclosure obligations under standard procurement procedures would have entailed revealing critical details about the Bundeswehr's tactical communication systems. Therefore, the content and specifications of the procurement project were allowed to remain confidential. The court argued that even limited disclosure could have created significant security risks, thereby justifying the invocation of Article 346(1)(b) TFEU to preserve confidentiality.²⁷⁶

4.4.4. GROUND: URGENCY

After the Russian invasion of Ukraine, urgency has become an increasingly important justification for invoking Article 346 TFEU in Germany. Urgency is not a ground explicitly mentioned in Article 346, but it has been indirectly accepted by German authorities and courts as a factor. This development is most clearly seen in the *Verg 22/23* case.²⁷⁷ The Court explicitly recognized that the deterioration of the security environment created a need for the Bundeswehr to acquire secure communication systems.

Moreover, the purchase of the 62 H145 helicopters could also be an example where urgency was the main ground of invocation. The source suggests that Germany invoked Article 346 TFEU based on urgency, although no supporting sources for this claim are provided.²⁷⁸ Besides, the purchase of 155mm SMART ammunition is also likely to be at least grounded in urgency concerns. Parliamentary questions are raised on whether the tender was awarded under Article 346 or under an expedited procurement, suggesting that urgency is highly valued in the decision-making process.²⁷⁹

From conversations with academics and practitioners involved in the procurement processes in Germany, it has become clear that the BAAINBw is often plagued by slow, bureaucratic procedures and a strong internal fear of legal challenges.²⁸⁰ This is also the reason why the German Armed Forces Procurement Acceleration Act was passed.²⁸¹ However, this cautious culture in the BAAINB remains and amplifies the need for urgency in defence procurement. Delays

²⁷⁵ Personal communication with Marc Pauka (videocall, 2 May 2025); Personal communication with Marc Greitens (videocall, 5 May 2025); Personal Communication with Martin Trybus (videocall, 6 May 2025); Personal communication with Roland Haag (email, 13 May 2025).

²⁷⁶ *VII-Verg 22/23* [2023] (n 253), paras 125-126.

²⁷⁷ *VII-Verg 22/23* [2023] (n 253).

²⁷⁸ Noah Heinemann, 'What Are the Main Drivers of Member States' Defence Procurement Practices? The German Case' (ARES Group, 2025) <<https://www.iris-france.org/en/what-are-the-main-drivers-of-member-states-defence-procurement-practices-the-german-case/>> accessed 27 June 2025, pp 3-4.

²⁷⁹ Bundestag, 'Antwort der Bundesregierung auf die Kleine Anfrage der Fraktion der CDU/CSU: Munition in der Bundeswehr: Aktueller Sachstand, Bedarfe und Planungen' (Drucksache 20/4509, 14 November 2022) <<https://dserver.bundestag.de/btd/20/045/2004509.pdf>> accessed 27 June 2025, p 12.

²⁸⁰ Personal communication with Marc Pauka (videocall, 2 May 2025); Personal communication with Marc Greitens (videocall, 5 May 2025).

²⁸¹ Bundeswehrbeschaffungsbeschleunigungsgesetz 2022.

Chapter 4

caused by excessive bureaucracy and risk aversion make speed and simplicity critical factors when deciding to invoke Article 346 TFEU.

4.5. INTERIM CONCLUSION

Chapter 4 discussed how Germany applies Article 346 TFEU in law and practice within its defence procurement policy, and what the grounds for invocation are. It can be concluded that the legal framework, as established in sections 107(2) and 117 GWB, provides a national legal basis for invoking the exemption, especially for key defence technologies. Administratively, decisions are made within the BAANBw and the Ministry, and are subject to parliamentary oversight, though the process remains opaque.

In practice, Germany applied Article 346 TFEU restrictively before 2022, with courts often demanding very strict justifications. However, since the Russian invasion of Ukraine, both judicial interpretation and political practice have shifted significantly. The exemption is now used more frequently, with the main grounds for invocation being to protect strategic industries through direct awards, to accelerate procurement, and to ensure secrecy. Germany's approach to Article 346 shows a transition from formal legalism to pragmatic strategic application under evolving geopolitical conditions.

CHAPTER 5. LEGAL ANALYSIS OF THE APPLICATION OF ARTICLE 346 TFEU BY THE NETHERLANDS AND GERMANY

Having analyzed each country separately, it is adequate to execute an analysis of the data and literature retrieved and discussed. Therefore, chapter 5 provides a comparative and normative analysis of the application of Article 346 TFEU by the Netherlands and Germany. Firstly, section 5.1 briefly compares the security interests as echoed by each country. Section 5.2. compares the legal and administrative procedures of both countries to invoke the exemption. Section 5.3. offers a strictly comparative analysis of the invocations by Germany and the Netherlands. Building on that, section 5.4. provides a normative angle and discusses the legality of the invocations of Article 346 by Germany and the Netherlands. Each ground for invocation is discussed separately with a legal analysis of compliance with the legal framework established by the Court.

5.1. ESSENTIAL SECURITY INTERESTS

Germany's security interests regarding the military goals are very similar to those of the Netherlands.²⁸² Both value autonomous military action, defence against hybrid and digital threats, and fulfilment of NATO obligations. Each of these goals necessitates a wide spectrum of capabilities and threats to be prepared for.

However, regarding the industrial capabilities, differences appear. The Netherlands has specifically targeted five industrial-technological capabilities in which it wants to be largely autonomous, and five areas in which it wants to innovate. Especially the maritime capabilities stand out, for which a high degree of autonomy is regarded as essential. Germany, on the other hand, has identified thirteen broad 'key technologies' under which almost any procurement project could fall. For land-based systems, the German automotive sector plays an important role through collaboration and as a source for technological expertise.

5.2. LEGAL AND ADMINISTRATIVE PROCEDURE OF INVOKING ARTICLE 346 TFEU

The differing national procedural approach to Article 346 TFEU between the Netherlands and Germany manifests a difference in both law and administration. In the Netherlands, Article 346 is not codified in national legislation, and its application is not subject to a formalized procedure.²⁸³ The Dutch Ministry can invoke the exemption flexibly and with limited internal or external formalized procedural steps. This means that projects involving Article 346 can move forward quickly, with minimal delay caused by legal review. Although legal review in principle remains possible in the Netherlands, market participants apparently enjoy weaker legal protection compared to Germany. While the Dutch approach may lack formal, rigorous procedures, it may also allow the Netherlands to act fast in urgent situations.

In Germany, on the other hand, Article 346 TFEU is codified into national law through sections 107(2) and 117 GWB.²⁸⁴ This provision in itself does not necessitate a large-scale review

²⁸² See sections 3.1. and 4.1. for the facts.

²⁸³ See section 3.2. for the facts.

²⁸⁴ See section 4.2. for the facts.

of the legality of invoking Article 346. To the contrary, it could be argued that the specification that section 107(2) provides could also mean a more concise casuistic review. However, for Germany, this is not the case, as the application of the exemption appears to require an extensive internal procedure. The procurement agency BAANBw carries out a labor-intensive internal assessment of necessity and proportionality. Ultimately, parliamentary approval is also needed if the procurement exceeds EUR 25 million.²⁸⁵ This administrative process is time-consuming and can result in procedural delay. These procedural burdens are not limited to Article 346. When procurement is carried out under the Directive, extensive reviews are required as well. As a result, although both frameworks entail considerable procedural requirements, the Article 346 route may still offer the faster alternative, especially when executed in a streamlined and less bureaucratic manner.

5.3. INVOCATIONS OF ARTICLE 346 TFEU

Several differences and similarities appear in the application of Article 346 TFEU between Germany and the Netherlands. The number and financial value of the invocations, as well as the grounds for invocations, are discussed. Unfortunately, a precise comparison between the number of or reasons behind Article 346 invocations by the Netherlands and Germany is not possible, primarily due to Germany's extremely restrictive transparency policy. Nevertheless, without exact figures, some conclusions can be drawn. Three differences and three similarities regarding the grounds of invocation will be discussed.

5.3.1. DIFFERENCES

Firstly, it appears that Germany has traditionally been more reluctant than the Netherlands to invoke Article 346 TFEU.²⁸⁶ The Netherlands more openly relies on the exemption, whereas Germany, until 2022, applied Article 346 conservatively. For the Netherlands, between 2020 and June 2025, at least thirteen tenders have been executed under Article 346, with an estimated value of EUR 20.2 billion.²⁸⁷ For six of these projects, it was disclosed before the start of the Russian invasion of Ukraine that Article 346 would be invoked. These six projects represent an estimated value of EUR 9.7 billion.

A second difference concerns the use of offset obligations.²⁸⁸ The Netherlands seems to systematically couple large foreign maritime procurements with obligations for offsets with Dutch firms. This is justified under the premise of strengthening the NLDTIB, where the Dutch industry cannot provide the prime contractor for the whole project. However, Germany typically does not need to apply such obligations. Instead, Germany should be able to directly award most of its main contracts to domestic firms without formal offset structures, as the German industry can provide the necessary capabilities needed to fulfill the contracts.

Thirdly, it seems that Germany values the extreme secrecy of its procurement process more than the Netherlands.²⁸⁹ Germany does not disclose any parliamentary documents about military procurement, and neither academics nor the defence industry itself receive information about the

²⁸⁵ Bundeshaushaltsordnung 1969, section 54(3); Wissenschaftliche Dienste des Deutschen Bundestages (2024) (n 32).

²⁸⁶ See sections 3.3. and 3.4. for the data and facts concerning the Netherlands and sections 4.3. and 4.4. for the data and facts concerning Germany.

²⁸⁷ For all values presented as ranges, the average of the range is taken. These averages are then summed to obtain the total.

²⁸⁸ See section 3.4.3. for the data and facts concerning the Netherlands and section 4.4.2. for the data and facts concerning Germany.

²⁸⁹ See section 3.4.4. for the data and facts concerning the Netherlands and section 4.4.3. for the data and facts concerning Germany.

legal or procedural basis of procurement decisions. The only streams of information are the annual publication that lists the largest ongoing defence projects,²⁹⁰ and the contract notices with specifications published on TED.²⁹¹ However, the annual publication does not list smaller procurement projects, nor the procurement procedures followed. Meanwhile, the competitive contract notices published on TED represent less than 2% of all expenditure on defence procurement.²⁹² In contrast, the Netherlands adopts a more transparent approach. While not all procurement decisions are disclosed, the Dutch government frequently informs Parliament when Article 346 TFEU is applied, particularly for large-scale projects.²⁹³ This often includes the rationale for the exemption. Although the Dutch Ministry has indicated that not every invocation of Article 346 is reported publicly, the level of transparency remains significantly higher than in Germany.

Lastly, it seems that since 2022, Germany has applied urgency as a ground for invoking Article 346 TFEU,²⁹⁴ which was approved by the German judiciary. Following the Russian invasion of Ukraine, the German government and courts have increasingly acknowledged that the speed required in current security conditions justifies derogations from standard EU procedures. However, in the Netherlands, the prevailing stance by civil servants is that Article 346 is not necessary to expedite procurement procedures, and that the exemptions under the Directive suffice.

5.3.2. SIMILARITIES

There also seem to be similarities regarding the application of Article 346 TFEU. Firstly, it appears that in both countries, the year 2022 marks a shifting year toward increasingly invoking Article 346.²⁹⁵ The worsening security situation entails larger procurements of defence equipment.²⁹⁶ Therefore, there have been signals that Article 346 is applied to a larger extent than before in both countries.

Secondly, for both countries, the dominant ground for the invocation of Article 346 TFEU concerns the protection and promotion of the defence industry.²⁹⁷ While for the Netherlands, this mostly includes the maritime sector, for Germany, this includes broader areas of defence production, since there is only little equipment it *cannot* provide on its own. Both procurement policies explicitly aim to support national firms through direct awards. This is visible through the projects, which all, except two Dutch projects, concerned the national respective industries.

²⁹⁰ Bundesministerium der Verteidigung, 19. Bericht des Bundesministeriums der Verteidigung zu Rüstungsangelegenheiten: Teil 1 (2024) <<https://www.bmvg.de/resource/blob/5820310/c30ac0f6b6437838720d9d7e1298f6a8/19-ruestungsbericht-teil-1-data.pdf>> accessed 27 June 2025.

²⁹¹ For German tenders published on TED, see: TED, 'Search results' (TED, 2025) <<https://ted.europa.eu/en/search/result?buyer-country=DEU&legal-basis=32009L0081&search-scope=ACTIVE>> accessed 27 June 2025.

²⁹² Between 2016 and 2018, on average only 1.8% of defence equipment was tendered competitively under the Directive by Germany, see: Loannides 2020 (n 5), p 93.

²⁹³ See Annex I.

²⁹⁴ See sections 3.4.5. for the data and facts concerning the Netherlands and sections 4.4.4. for the data and facts concerning Germany.

²⁹⁵ See section 3.3.1. for the data and facts concerning the Netherlands and section 4.3.2. for the data and facts concerning Germany.

²⁹⁶ In the Netherlands and Germany, the defence budgets nearly doubled, see: Zandee 2024 (n 137), p 2; Bernd Lucke and Dirk Meyer, 'Germany's New Constitutional Rules on Public Debt: An Analysis of Debt Sustainability and Intergenerational Fairness' (2025) 16 International Journal of Financial Research 30.

²⁹⁷ See sections 3.4.1. and 3.4.2. for the data and facts concerning the Netherlands and section 4.4.1. for the data and facts concerning Germany.

5.4. LEGALITY OF THE INVOCATIONS

While Article 346 TFEU allows Member States to take the measures necessary for the protection of their essential security interests, the Court has consistently held that such derogations from EU procurement rules must be interpreted strictly and applied only in exceptional cases. The legality of direct awards, competitive procurement procedures under Article 346, offsets, secrecy measures, and urgency is therefore assessed according to the criteria established by the Court.

5.4.1. GROUND: DIRECT AWARDS TO SUPPORT THE NATIONAL DEFENCE INDUSTRY

Concerning the legality of the invocations of Article 346 TFEU to directly award a contract to a specific domestic firm, the actions taken by both countries raise concerns. In the Dutch and German context, the direct awards reflect the strategic priority to maintain industrial capabilities; for the Netherlands, this concerns largely the maritime industry, for Germany, this concerns a broader industrial base identified as key technologies. To justify these direct awards, there are two arguments to be made.

Firstly, it could be demonstrated that, absent such measures, the ability to produce equipment essential to national security is removed. However, the consistent direct awarding of contracts with an extremely high value to specific domestic firms without competition could be viewed as exceeding what is necessary for national security. In the Dutch case, it is evident that Damen and Thales already hold extensive high-value naval contracts, with long order books, and it will take many years for the equipment to be delivered. Therefore, unless concrete evidence can be provided that the defence industry of each respective country would not survive without the directly awarded contracts, and that each direct award is indispensable for protecting essential security interests, such practices may not withstand legal scrutiny.

Secondly, beyond industrial survival, an argument could be made based on security of supply. Even where companies are commercially successful abroad, a Member State can rightfully aim to be the main client of a domestic firm. Being the main client gives the state negotiable options for special treatment. For example, a state can maintain a preferential position in terms of priority access and priority delivery. Therefore, maintaining strong ties with domestic firms ensures not only industrial continuity, but also operational readiness and strategic autonomy in critical times.

I would therefore argue that while the protection of national security is a legitimate concern, extensive use of Article 346 TFEU of high-value contracts can go beyond the narrow scope of Article 346. On the other hand, states are allowed to ensure their position as the main client. Maintaining strong domestic firms and ties to those firms not only contributes to industrial policy goals but also ensures operational readiness. However, if severe conflict were to break out, governments can still, in any case, intervene to cease exports of military equipment and redirect production capacity towards national needs.

5.4.2. GROUND: COMPETITIVE PROCUREMENT PROCEDURE UNDER ARTICLE 346 TFEU

Direct awards to a specific firm constitute a highly restrictive measure, while the invocation of Article 346 TFEU must be proportional, meaning Member States must take the least restrictive actions possible to achieve the security objective. In many cases, a project awarded under some form of competition through a negotiated procedure under Article 346 would suffice to protect the essential security interests. Through this procedure, it is possible to support and protect the national defence industry and include requirements in the tender that are not permitted under the Directive.

While no German invocation with this ground was found, a Dutch example is the *Onderzeeboten* tender. In this specific case, the Ministry undertook a restricted tender without publication with three pre-selected shipyards, for which Article 346 was invoked to enable the government to exercise significantly broader discretion in formulating the criteria and procedure than would be possible under the Directive.

5.4.3. GROUND: OFFSETS

The legality of using Article 346 TFEU to impose offsets is controversial. Offsets must be proportionate and directly linked to essential security interests, while offsets aimed solely at economic benefits, such as industrial policy or employment, are incompatible with EU law. As explained, there do not appear to be German cases in which significant offsets were demanded. Therefore, this analysis focuses on the Dutch context.

In the Dutch case, I make a distinction between offsets to large companies and SMES. For large companies, similarly to the direct awards, I would argue that maritime offsets through the invocation of Article 346 TFEU are likely not permitted under the established legal framework. As explained, Dutch shipyards are, to put it mildly, in a financially healthy position, which removes necessity. However, this conclusion must be nuanced in light of the importance of maintaining a special relationship with domestic suppliers. By using a mix of offsets and direct awards, the state can secure its status as a main client and thereby ensure priority access, especially in times of crisis.

On the other hand, offsets to smaller and more vulnerable industries, I would argue, are legal. Targeting small SMEs that are active in niche industries designated as essential for national security may satisfy the criteria of Article 346 TFEU. As SMEs cannot operate independently and represent just one link in the overall supply chain, they inevitably become reliant on offset arrangements. Here, offsets can support capability gaps that are necessary for national security. This approach aligns with the Commission's view that Article 346 may be invoked to protect the national industry, so long as each measure is limited to what is strictly required for

5.4.4. GROUND: SECRECY AND CONFIDENTIALITY

Under both Articles 346(1)(a) and 346(1)(b) TFEU, Member States can take security measures with regard to defence equipment procedures and the accompanied information disclosure to (1) classify entire procurement projects as secret, and (2) keep technical specifications confidential from producers and the public. For example, broad groups of producers can be excluded from tenders by invoking Article 346 TFEU.²⁹⁸

Since it is not known to which project category 1 is applied, it is hardly possible to execute a normative analysis. At the same time, there are, as discussed, signs that Germany might be excessively using Article 346 TFEU for this purpose. While no conclusions can be drawn as to the legality, it is doubtful whether this is legal, and the German government should try to maximize transparency.

For the latter category, the Directive already provides the restricted procedure, negotiated procedure with publication, or the competitive dialogue, to which the number of bidders can be limited to three pre-selected companies.²⁹⁹ Under these procedures, a contract notice without

²⁹⁸ Elisabetta Manunza and Nathan Meershoek, 'Een juridische onderbouwing om het Ecosysteem Duurzame Strategische Samenwerking Onbemande Systemen uit te zonderen van aanbestedingsverplichtingen op grond van Artikel 346 VWEU' (Utrecht University Centre for Public Procurement & RENFORCE 2024), p 23; Personal communication with Jorn Bleijs (Utrecht, 22 May 2024).

²⁹⁹ Directive 2009/81/EC, art 38(3).

specifications is published on TED,³⁰⁰ and only shortlisted candidates subsequently receive the technical documentation. This mechanism is designed to protect sensitive information while maintaining competition and transparency. Besides, the negotiated procedure without prior publication under Article 28 of the Directive cannot be applied for confidentiality reasons. Confidentiality or secrecy requirements fall instead under Article 346 TFEU (the defence-and-security carve-out). Therefore, the existence of confidential elements in a procurement process does not normally justify recourse to Article 346. Derogation from the Directive is only proportional where the specifications are so sensitive that they can only be shared with one supplier.

This confidentiality ground was used in four identified procurements: *Onderzeeboten*, *Foxtrot*, *Vervanging MRAD & SHORAD*, and the unspecified project the case *Verg 22/23* addressed. In the *Onderzeeboten* project, Article 346(1)(b) TFEU was invoked, and the Minister argued that disclosure of technical and operational data would compromise both national strategic deterrence and allied confidentiality obligations.³⁰¹ Given the inherently clandestine nature of submarine operations, it is reasonable to accept that the specifications of the procurement should be handled with utmost confidentiality. However, as it is known, the contract was competitively tendered among three companies. Therefore, while the invocation of Article 346 TFEU might have provided for easy means to increase confidentiality, confidentiality alone could not have legally led to an invocation of Article 346. The *Foxtrot* project, on the other hand, concerns a potential invocation of Article 346(1)(a) TFEU for communications technology, including cryptographic keys and radio protocols. For communication so closely related to security between security personnel, it is essential to disclose information to as few people as necessary. Therefore, it is legal for the government to share the specifications of the project with only one company. Unfortunately, in *Vervanging MRAD&SHORAD*, the Minister did not elaborate why (the codification in the Directive of) Article 346(1)(a) was invoked to disapply the Directive. That said, the invocation was likely lawful given that the procurement included wireless communication systems and radar capabilities, of which the disclosure of technical specifications could significantly endanger national and allied operational security.

In Germany, the judiciary also confirmed the argument. In line with *Foxtrot*, the *Verg 22/23* decision upheld a closed tender under Article 346(1)(b) for tactical radio systems,³⁰² accepting that any procedural disclosure would expose critical interoperability and encryption data.

On top of that, the legality of the invocations by both countries is supported by the case *Commission v Poland*,³⁰³ in which the Court confirmed that Member States can invoke Article 346(1)(a) TFEU to protect classified or sensitive military information if disclosure would give rise to unacceptable risks to essential security interests. It is no longer contested that Article 346 TFEU can be invoked in these instances.

5.4.5. GROUND: URGENCY

The last ground concerns urgency in procuring equipment, which has proven important after sizeable deliveries to Ukraine started, which needed to be restocked. While it is true that Article 346 TFEU can be easy to administer and will provide tools to quickly procure equipment, neither the Netherlands nor Germany may lawfully invoke Article 346 based on urgency alone. The Court has made clear that Article 346 is a security exception, and not an exemption to serve administrative

³⁰⁰ Pursuant to Directive 2009/81/EC, Article 30.

³⁰¹ *Kamerstukken II* 2019-2020, 34225, nr. 25, p 31.

³⁰² *VII-Verg 22/23* [2023] (n 253).

³⁰³ *European Commission v Republic of Poland* [2023] (n 55).

convenience: derogations must be strictly necessary and proportionate to protect genuine essential security interests.

Where time-sensitive or urgent procurement is genuinely driven by security needs, the Directive itself provides a tailored mechanism: the negotiated procedure without prior publication. This procedure permits contracting authorities to negotiate directly with invited suppliers where circumstances do not allow time for open advertising. This can happen in any case of extreme urgency, which can be declared by a Member State.³⁰⁴

It should be emphasized that even the negotiated procedure without publication is a drastic measure. Less restrictive and more competitive alternatives, being the restricted procedure and negotiated procedure with notice, can all be completed in a minimum of thirty calendar days: ten days for the invitation to tender,³⁰⁵ a standstill period of ten days to allow for challenges,³⁰⁶ and ten days after signing for unsuccessful bidders to seek review.³⁰⁷ In essence, the negotiated procedure without publication can only be applied for urgency reasons if even this thirty-day period is too long.

The negotiated procedure without publication can be particularly useful in overheated markets where demand far outstrips supply and suppliers are unwilling or unable to engage in lengthy procurement processes. In such cases, the availability of defence products may change rapidly, and waiting thirty days to complete a formal tender procedure can result in the loss of delivery capacity. In this context, the negotiated procedure without prior publication allows the state to act with the necessary speed to secure production capacity before it is allocated elsewhere. However, this flexibility must be used cautiously, as such markets are also vulnerable to price inflation, reduced transparency, and political controversy and corruption, particularly when public contracts are awarded without competition.³⁰⁸

Urgency shortcuts to avoid formal procedures and administrative requirements do not qualify as security interests and cannot justify exclusion under Article 346 TFEU, since bureaucratic challenges must be resolved by governments themselves, and procedural inefficiencies can be resolved through well-functioning acceleration methods under the Directive. Concerning bureaucratic challenges in defence procurement, these are matters for national administrative reform, not Treaty derogations. Member States must address procedural inefficiencies through domestic law or internal process improvements rather than by importing speed as a new ground for derogation.³⁰⁹ Resorting to Article 346 on urgency grounds would undermine the Directive's goals to improve and harmonize the EDTIB and run contrary to the Court's insistence that security exemptions be confined to genuine security risks, not administrative inconvenience.³¹⁰

An important addition is that, in the future, the proposed amendment of the Directive would add a Dynamic Purchasing System under Article 29a, which could offer an additional acceleration tool for routine defence purchases.³¹¹ Instead of evaluating suppliers repetitively for each contract,

³⁰⁴ Directive 2009/81/EC, art 28(1)(c) and (d).

³⁰⁵ *ibid*, art 33(7)(b).

³⁰⁶ *ibid*, art 57(2).

³⁰⁷ *ibid*, art bid, 59(1).

³⁰⁸ Jolien Grandia and Rianna Warsen, 'Procurement under pressure: Shifting governance strategies in turbulent times' [2023] *Public Management Review* <<https://doi.org/10.1080/14719037.2023.2281973>> accessed 27 June 2025; In the Sywert van der Lienden face-mask case, Dutch authorities awarded a EUR 100 million face mask contract in 2020 under urgent conditions. Later, it emerged that the deal was routed through a private company and generated millions in profits, triggering criminal and civil claims, see: Jan-Hein Strop and Stefan Vermeulen, *Sywerts miljoenen: De jacht op het mondkapjesgoud* (Follow the Money 2022).

³⁰⁹ This analysis is also shared by: Recihling & Vollert 2023 (n 266), p 153; Trybus & Friton 2023 (n 231), p 6.

³¹⁰ Marc Pauka, '„Zeitenwende“ und „Kriegstüchtigkeit“ im Vergaberecht (Teil 2)' [2025] *VergabeR* 224.

³¹¹ European Commission 2025 (n 48), pp 25-26.

authorities can qualify suppliers for categories once. For each subsequent tender, only screened suppliers relevant to that category are invited to submit bids. This two-stage approach, with one initial qualification followed by a quick tender specific to the category of equipment, reduces time and administrative work for routine purchases.

5.5. INTERIM-CONCLUSION

This chapter compared how the Netherlands and Germany apply Article 346 TFEU in practice and how these practices align with EU law. It is concluded that, as to the legal framework, Germany has formally implemented Article 346 through section 107(2) GWB, while the Netherlands applies Article 346 informally through ministerial discretion without a codified framework.

Concerning the number of applications, Germany follows a formal, statute-based approach, increasingly invoking Article 346 TFEU for urgent procurement needs since 2022. The Netherlands uses Article 346 mainly for maritime defence, without proof that its application has increased after 2022.

Concerning legality, direct awards and offsets, it is argued that the measures taken can meet the necessity and proportionality requirements for some projects, although it is doubtful whether the invocations are also lawful for industries whose subsistence is already certain. Also secrecy meets the necessity and proportionality requirements under EU law. However, urgency, as invoked in Germany, remains controversial and likely exceeds the limits of the current legal framework.

CHAPTER 6. EUROPEAN STRATEGIC AUTONOMY

Having analyzed the past and current application of Article 346 TFEU, this chapter addresses the final dimension of the thesis: the potential for legal or policy reform to reconcile national sovereignty with European coordination in the field of defence procurement.

The findings of the preceding chapters have demonstrated that Article 346 TFEU is invoked differently across Member States, both legally and in practice. The divergence in application raises questions about the coherence of the EU's defence procurement framework and the EU's ability to create a more integrated and competitive EDTIB. In the introduction, the problem was established that Member States resort to non-transparent or protectionist procedures under Article 346. Such practices undermine (1) competition and economies of scale, and (2) interoperability of equipment in the EDTIB. This chapter, therefore, positions Article 346 within the broader objective of European strategic autonomy and explores options to improve coherence without undermining the sovereign right of Member States to protect their essential security interests.

Section 6.1. clarifies the meaning of European strategic autonomy. Section 6.2. discusses the most recent actions the European Commission is taking to improve coordination and coherence in defence procurement. Moreover, I would like to propose two possible solutions. Sections 6.3. and 6.4. evaluate each category of potential reform: interpretative guidance by the European Commission and intergovernmental coordination mechanisms. Section 6.5. concludes this chapter by assessing the feasibility and desirability of the options.

6.1. THE MEANING AND IMPORTANCE OF STRATEGIC AUTONOMY

The concept of European strategic autonomy has gained prominence in the EU's political and policy discourse,³¹² particularly since the publication of the EU Security Strategy in 2016³¹³ and the intensification of geopolitical instability following Russia's invasion of Ukraine in 2022. While the notion of strategic autonomy originated in the context of security and defence, it has since evolved into a broader policy objective. In the defence sphere, strategic autonomy refers to the capacity of the EU to act independently when necessary to defend its interests and values, without being structurally dependent on third countries for critical capabilities, technologies, or decisions.

Strategic autonomy does not require complete self-sufficiency or the exclusion of external partnerships, particularly with NATO and the US. Rather, it is a model of resilient interdependence that emphasizes the EU's capacity to act autonomously where necessary, which includes the development and availability of key industrial, technological, and operational capabilities.³¹⁴

That is why, in March 2025, the European Commission launched *ReArm Europe Plan/Readiness 2030* as a response to the deteriorating security environment and to expeditiously strengthen European defence and close military capability gaps.³¹⁵ Financially, the initiative seeks to mobilize EUR 800 billion from a combination of economic sources. This will involve raising

³¹² European External Action Service 2016 (n 25); European External Action Service 2022 (n 24).

³¹³ European External Action Service 2016 (n 25), pp 4, 9, 19, 45, 46; European Parliamentary Research Service, 'EU Strategic Autonomy 2013–2023: From Concept to Capacity' (Briefing, European Parliament 2022) <[https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2022/733589/EPRS_BRI\(2022\)733589_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2022/733589/EPRS_BRI(2022)733589_EN.pdf)> accessed 27 June 2025.; Cinzia Alcidì and others, *What ways and means for a real strategic autonomy of the EU in the economic field?* (Visits and Publications Unit 2023); College of Europe Podcast (Bruges), 'College Security and Defence Podcast (CSDP)' (6 January 2025) <<https://open.spotify.com/episode/0jblBohDWpTG3DMXXroFZp>> accessed 27 June 2025.

³¹⁴ For a short overview: Alcidì & others 2023 (n 313), pp 4-9.

³¹⁵ European Commission and High Representative of the Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy 2025 (n 7).

EUR 150 billion from EU-backed loans, and EUR 750 billion by attracting private capital and loosening fiscal rules.

While the efforts are commendable, the promotion of European strategic autonomy, requires a recalibration of the balance between national discretion under Article 346 TFEU and the EU's collective interest in a functioning and integrated defence market.

6.2. NEXT STEPS: ACTIONS UNDERWAY

The European Commission has taken different actions in the past to improve coherence and coordination of defence procurement. The EU attempted to achieve this through financial mechanisms, including OCCAR, PESCO, and the European Defence Fund. All these mechanisms contained certain cooperation obligations and a prerequisite for finance. The newest tool in town is the Readiness 2030 initiative. The EUR 150 billion EU-backed funding is only available to ten products that constitute the most acute EU-wide capability gaps.³¹⁶ As an incentive for coordinated procurement, each funded project must involve at least two Member States.³¹⁷ Besides, the White Paper repeatedly stresses the need for collaboration and coordination in procurement, reiterating the goal previously set in the *European Defence Industrial Strategy* that 40% of defence procurement should be executed collaboratively.³¹⁸

Moreover, the proposal for amending the Directive will also give the Member States more incentives for cooperation. Under the proposed Article 10(a), Member States can empower central purchasing bodies to conduct defence procurements on behalf of all contracting authorities from different Member States. By channeling purchases through a single, specialized entity, authorities avoid running parallel tender processes. Article 28(3)(d) temporarily allows the negotiated procedure without prior publication for supply contracts awarded by at least three Member States together. Until January 2031, purchases of identical or minimally modified military equipment can proceed via a negotiated procedure without prior publication.

Despite these initiatives, real coordination remains limited: the two-state rule under Readiness 2030 does not require alignment of standards, and projects may qualify for funding while still having divergent priorities or goals. Additionally, the White Paper lacks transparency or requirements. The incentives for cooperation in the legislative proposal are a step forward but remain insufficient: participation in central purchasing bodies is just an extra possibility, and the negotiated multi-state procedure under Article 28(3)(d) expires by 2031. As a result, Member States can still invoke Article 346 TFEU unilaterally and without disclosure without disclosing their plans, which will undermine coordination.

6.3. SOFT LAW: INTERPRETATIVE GUIDANCE BY THE COMMISSION

One strategy to improve coherence in the application of Article 346 TFEU does not require changes to primary or secondary legislation, but can be implemented through the Commission's existing

³¹⁶ Commission, 'Proposal for a Council Regulation establishing the Security Action for Europe (SAFE) through the reinforcement of the European defence industry Instrument' COM (2025) 122 final, p 17.

³¹⁷ *ibid*, p 15; European Commission and High Representative of the Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy 2025 (n 7), p 16.

³¹⁸ *ibid*, p 20; Commission and High Representative of the Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy, 'Joint Communication: A New European Defence Industrial Strategy: Achieving EU readiness through a responsive and resilient European Defence Industry' (Joint Communication) JOIN (2024) 10 final, p 10.

powers. The Commission may autonomously pursue two complementary approaches: the development of soft law and the initiation of infringement proceedings.

The first approach involves issuing interpretative communications. The Interpretative Communication on Article 346 TFEU is only six pages and stems from 2006.³¹⁹ A new Communication as a non-binding instrument clarifies the legal conditions under which Member States may derogate from EU procurement law on grounds of national security. While the Interpretative Communication was complemented by additional communications and notices concerning specific aspects of the Directive, particularly on offsets and exclusions,³²⁰ it is now time to publish a new communication to integrate new case law and the new geopolitical situation in a single, more extensive document. Agreeing with this view, the European Parliament adopted a resolution in April 2025, which stated that it ‘calls on the Commission to make suggestions for an interpretation of Article 346 in line with the current reality of an interdependent security architecture in the EU’.³²¹ By updating the outdated interpretative communication and outlining acceptable grounds for invocation and the limits of discretion under Article 346, abuse of the exemption can be prevented.

The second tool available to the Commission is the initiation of infringement proceedings under Articles 348 and 258 TFEU. Where it is considered that a Member State has improperly invoked Article 346 TFEU, the Commission may formally request compliance and ultimately bring the case before the Court. Since the start of the Russian invasion of Ukraine, the Commission has started only one infringement proceeding against Czechia.³²² Publishing a comprehensive new communication on Article 346 and coupling it with a firmer, more proactive approach to infringement proceedings should reduce the frequency with which Article 346 is invoked.

6.4. INTERGOVERNMENTAL COORDINATION MECHANISMS

Another possible avenue for enhancing coherence in the application of Article 346 TFEU is to establish some form of a communication obligation through the intergovernmental dimension of the TFEU. Articles 347 and 348 para 1 TFEU enable the Commission and a Member State to enter into consultations where there is a dispute about the scope or legality of measures taken under Article 346. Although the procedure is currently facultative and reactive, triggered only in the event of disagreement, it does show that the EU treaties provide a legal foundation for intergovernmental communication on sensitive security-related measures. This procedural framework could be adapted to introduce a communication obligation.

Similar to the consultation duty under Article 32 TEU in the Common Foreign and Security Policy, the communication obligation under the CSDP could require Member States to notify the Commission *ex ante* and confidentially when invoking Article 346 TFEU for defence procurement contracts. Such a notification mechanism does not alter the legal status of Article 346 as a safeguard of sovereignty, nor would it confer power to the Commission. Rather, it would strengthen the EDTIB in three ways.³²³

³¹⁹ European Commission 2006 (n 60).

³²⁰ European Commission 2016 (2) (n 82); Directorate-General Internal Market and Services 2010 (n 33).

³²¹ European Parliament 2025 (2) (n 8).

³²² European Commission, ‘The Commission calls on Czechia to comply with the Defence Procurement Directive’ (*European Commission*, 7 February 2024) <https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/inf_24_301> accessed 27 June 2025.

³²³ Meershoek 2023 (3) (n 2), pp 237–239. Meershoek similarly argues that transparency obligations can improve coordination and reduce fragmentation in EU military procurement. While this thesis takes a comparable position on the value of transparency and coordination, it emphasizes the potential for confidential, *ex ante* notification obligations

First, it would enhance transparency, which is a key principle of EU public procurement law. In the Directive, transparency primarily ensures non-discrimination. As confirmed by the Court in *Telaustria*,³²⁴ transparency also has broader systemic functions: it enables effective judicial protection,³²⁵ and fosters competitive markets.

Secondly, transparency in the defence context could serve as a tool to reinforce political solidarity among Member States. Transparency in this domain would help build the foundations of a shared security culture. A regularized exchange of information could promote joint procurement and connect member states aiming to buy similar equipment. Moreover, it could also foster convergence in national interpretations of Article 346 TFEU.

Thirdly, principally, a communication obligation would give effect to the principle of sincere cooperation under Article 4(3) TEU. It would balance defence integration that respects national discretion in matters of security, while also advancing the EU's collective interest in a transparent, and hopefully more coherent procurement framework.

Applying this framework to the invocations studied, it is my expectation that this procedure would be especially beneficial in multinational contracts such as the replacement of *M-fregatten* and the *Caracal air assault vehicles*. In these projects, transparency would signal to other EU governments that a significant defence project is underway. By knowing in advance that Member States are jointly procuring, a notification could give rise to discussions, clarifying which countries wish to join and which prefer to remain outside. As a result, joint procurement that operates without dedicated EU funding would still be encouraged to involve more Member States.

Moreover, especially with large projects like the *Onderzeeboten* project, transparency would be politically beneficial. A confidential notification would clarify why offsets are justified and create a better judicial record, thereby mitigating risks of overstepping proportionality. Furthermore, communication is essential to prevent political tensions between Member States. The diplomatic feud as a result of the AUKUS agreement, where the US suddenly cancelled a major submarine deal with France,³²⁶ elucidates the risks of excluding key partners from strategic procurement decisions. A notification obligation could help avoid political trouble.

6.5. INTERIM-CONCLUSION

This chapter looked at the existing plans to improve defence coordination and asked what legal or policy actions at the EU level could be taken to improve the legal framework around Article 346 TFEU in the light of European strategic autonomy.

Although the existing plans are laudable, they remain insufficient. Two realistic actions stand out to really improve the legal framework. First, the European Commission could issue an updated and more extensive interpretative communication clarifying the limits of Article 346 TFEU. This would improve legal certainty and discourage inconsistent use of the exemption. This should be connected to more stringent control and infringement proceedings where necessary.

specifically in relation Article 346 TFEU. This system would function as an intergovernmental mechanism for coordination; it is in line with and does not alter the safeguard function of the provision.

³²⁴ Case C-324/98 *Telaustria Verlags GmbH and Telefonadress GmbH v Telekom Austria AG* [2000] ECR I-10745, paras 61-62.

³²⁵ An essential principle in the EU legal order: Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union [2012] OJ C326/391, art 47; TFEU, art 19(1).

³²⁶ George Parker and others, 'Aukus: How transatlantic allies turned on each other over China's Indo-Pacific threat', (*Financial Times*, Washington and Paris, 24 September 2021) <<https://www.ft.com/content/06f95e54-732e-4508-bc92-c3752904ba67>> accessed 27 June 2025.

Second, a communication obligation could require Member States to notify the Commission when invoking Article 346 for major defence procurements. Both measures respect national sovereignty and enhance transparency with the goal of better coordinating in defence procurement. They represent feasible steps toward a more integrated and strategically autonomous EU defence framework.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The war in Ukraine has fundamentally reshaped the European security landscape, triggering unprecedented levels of defence spending and a renewed political will to strengthen European unity in the face of external threats. While the EU has long acted as an economic powerhouse through the customs union, it has historically lacked corresponding political or military integration. Belgian Foreign Minister Mark Eyskens aptly described the EU in 1991 as ‘an economic giant, a political dwarf, and a military worm’.³²⁷

Defence still is the instrument of last resort of national sovereignty, and thus outside the scope of EU integration. However, the growing interdependence of Member States’ legal and economic systems, combined with the current geopolitical developments, entails an assessment of this position. Article 346 TFEU plays a central role in the political reformation; this provision allows Member States to derogate from EU rules to protect essential security interests. As the EU progressively takes on a role in the defence of the Member States, Article 346 TFEU can function as a source of uncontrolled fragmentation. By contrast, Article 346 should ideally not act as a barrier to integration but rather as a narrowly applied safeguard.

To better understand Article 346 TFEU, this research aimed to elucidate how Article 346 TFEU is applied both in law and in practice, addressing a gap in European legal scholarship. Prior to Russia’s invasion of Ukraine, the invocation of Article 346 by Member States received limited attention. However, in the new geopolitical landscape, Article 346 might play a central role. This study contributes to a better understanding of how this provision’s application may shape, and be shaped by, the evolving context of European defence integration.

This thesis sought to answer the central research question: ‘How do the different national approaches of the Netherlands and Germany to the application of Article 346 TFEU in defence procurement align with the legal conditions established under EU law, and how could potential negative effects on EU strategic autonomy be mitigated?’ Based on my research, several conclusions can be drawn. The answer to the main research question emerges from the cumulative conclusions of the sub-questions.

The analysis of the Dutch approach shows that the Netherlands primarily invokes Article 346 TFEU to support its maritime defence industry. The Dutch government uses Article 346 for direct awards to domestic firms, to impose offset obligations, and to ensure secrecy and confidentiality. Urgency is invoked less frequently, as the Netherlands tends to rely on the crisis clauses of the Directive for such cases. The procedure for invocation is flexible and policy-driven, without a formalized legal process. The Dutch approach is relatively transparent, and parliament is regularly informed about large procurements, although not all invocations are made public.

In contrast, Germany’s application of Article 346 TFEU is focused on direct awards, secrecy and confidentiality, and urgency. Germany has made increased use of the exemption following recent geopolitical developments. Importantly, German practice is less transparent, and there is minimal public disclosure of specific invocations. The Bundestag’s involvement does ensure oversight for major contracts, but little is published.

Both Member States mainly use Article 346 TFEU for: (1) direct awards to support the national defence technological and industrial base, and (2) tenders based on secrecy and confidentiality. While the Netherlands additionally uses Article 346 to arrange competitive

³²⁷ Mark Eyskens, quoted in ‘War in the Gulf: Europe; Gulf Fighting Shatters Europeans’ Fragile Unity’ (*New York Times*, London, 25 January 1991)

procedures under Article 346 and for offset purposes, Germany seems to apply the Article for urgency reasons.

It is shown that Article 346 TFEU, although interpreted strictly, is in practice often applied more broadly than strictly necessary, in particular due to a lack of transparency: many invocations are not published or internationally discussed, but only shared within a small circle. This practice contributes to fragmentation between Member States and undermines uniformity and legal certainty within the internal market.

In order to mitigate the negative effects on European strategic autonomy, actionable advice is to create more room for joint defence procurement without unnecessary secrecy, both through soft policy instruments (e.g., interpretative guidelines) and through intergovernmental coordination mechanisms introducing disclosure criteria for Article 346 TFEU invocations. This can protect national essential interests and at the same time strengthen Europe's interoperability, market integration, and strategic resilience. These instruments should not rely on internal market logic, but instead be constitutionally based on the CSDP.

In short, the answer to the main research question is the following. Dutch and German approaches to the application of Article 346 TFEU reflect national policy choices and do not always align with the strict legal conditions established under EU law. While both Member States invoke the provision to safeguard essential security interests, their practices differ in terms of transparency, procedure, frequency of use, and grounds. These divergent approaches contribute to a lack of defence equipment interoperability and market fragmentation. To mitigate the threat to European strategic autonomy, greater coordination and transparency are needed.

This research contributes to the academic community by offering an in-depth comparative analysis of Article 346 TFEU in the field of defence procurement. By clarifying how legal interpretation and practical application diverge, and subsequently also positioning this knowledge in the broader debate on European security, this thesis provides a foundation for legal and political debate in the future.

It must be acknowledged that this research was constrained by the lack of access to confidential or classified information. This constitutes a notable limitation. The research was based on publicly available sources, which limits the ability to fully assess the number and legal reasoning of certain invocations.

The limitation does open the door for future research. Future research would preferably be in cooperation with Member State governments and the European Commission, and would thereby gain access to confidential information. Moreover, given the limited resources, this research only compared two EU Member States. Future research could expand the comparative analysis to include other Member States with distinct industrial profiles. A separate idea for future research would be to further empirically examine what the concrete effects of Article 346 TFEU invocations are on the development of the EDTIB. This includes assessing how the exemption strengthens or weakens long-term competitiveness, interoperability, and innovation capacity. These broader studies would allow for a more comprehensive understanding of how Article 346 is applied across the EU and how this influences European security.

SAMENVATTING

Deze thesis onderzoekt hoe Nederland en Duitsland artikel 346 van het Verdrag betreffende de werking van de Europese Unie (VWEU) toepassen bij defensieaanbestedingen en wat dit betekent voor de strategische autonomie van de EU. Hoewel het artikel lidstaten toestaat af te wijken van EU-recht om essentiële veiligheidsbelangen te beschermen, leidt het in de praktijk tot versplintering systemen, inefficiëntie en ondermijning van een geïntegreerde Europese defensiemarkt. De Richtlijn Defensieaanbestedingen 2009/81/EG heeft dit slechts beperkt kunnen tegengaan. Door middel van doctrinair en empirisch onderzoek wordt geanalyseerd hoe beide landen het artikel toepassen, in hoeverre dit in lijn is met het EU-recht, en welke beleidsmaatregelen nodig zijn om meer coherentie en Europese samenwerking te bevorderen.

Het juridische kader van artikelen 346(1)(a) en 346(1)(b) VWEU staat lidstaten toe af te wijken van EU-recht om essentiële veiligheidsbelangen te beschermen. Deze uitzondering wordt door het Hof van Justitie strikt uitgelegd. Artikel 346(1)(b) mag alleen worden toegepast bij militair materieel (zoals gedefinieerd in de 1958 Wapenlijst), op basis van concrete veiligheidsbelangen mits noodzakelijk en proportioneel. Dual-use goederen vallen slechts onder de uitzondering als ze specifiek voor militair gebruik zijn ontworpen. Ook artikel 346(1)(a), over informatievrijgave, vereist strikte toetsing. Wel is enige verruiming met betrekking tot de strikte toetsing vanwege de verslechterde veiligheidssituatie in Europa. De handhaving van het gebruik van artikel 346 VWEU vindt plaats via artikel 258 of 348 VWEU.

In Nederland bestaat geen vast procedure om artikel 346 VWEU formeel te activeren. Wel informeert de minister bij opdrachten boven EUR 50 miljoen de Tweede Kamer via zogenoemde ‘A-brieven’. Nederland definieert zijn ‘essentiële veiligheidsbelangen’ via overheidsdocumenten, waarbij vooral maritieme capaciteiten centraal staan. Uit openbare parlementaire documenten blijkt dat Nederland in dertien concrete gevallen artikel 346 heeft ingeroepen. De voornaamste gronden voor toepassing zijn directe gunningen, het organiseren van een procedure onder competitie met meer vrijheid onder artikel 346, offsetverplichtingen, geheimhouding van technische gegevens en, wellicht in kleine mate, efficiëntie. De toepassing richt zich vrijwel uitsluitend op de maritieme sector, met bedrijven als Damen en Thales als vaste ontvangers. Sinds de Russische invasie van Oekraïne is het gebruik van het artikel toegenomen, mede door het verruimde defensiebudget, al biedt de Richtlijn Defensieaanbestedingen vaak al voldoende flexibiliteit voor snelle aanbesteding. Financieel gaat het om ongeveer EUR 20,2 miljard aan defensie-investeringen tot 2036, en circa 31% van de geplande uitgaven in 2024.

In Duitsland is het gebruik van artikel 346 VWEU vastgelegd in sectie 107(2) en 117 GWB, waarmee het juridisch kader formeel is verankerd in nationaal recht. De invulling van ‘essentiële veiligheidsbelangen’ wordt bepaald aan de hand van strategiedocumenten, waarin onder meer grote delen van de industriële basis worden aangemerkt als kritische technologieën waarvan het bestaan een essentieel veiligheidsbelang is. Hoewel er geen transparante rapportage bestaat, keurt het parlement defensiecontracten boven EUR 25 miljoen goed. Tot 2022 werd artikel 346 zelden ingeroepen en restrictief geïnterpreteerd door Duitse rechtbanken. Sinds de Russische invasie van Oekraïne is er echter sprake van een beleidsomslag: het gebruik van het artikel is toegenomen, waarbij directe gunningen, geheimhouding van projecten zelf en vertrouwelijkheid van technische specificaties, en snelheid vooropstaan. Met name het arrest *Verg 22/23* markeert een bredere interpretatie van de uitzondering, waarbij ook efficiëntie en geopolitieke dreiging als rechtvaardiging worden geaccepteerd.

Vervolgens is vergeleken en beoordeeld hoe Nederland en Duitsland artikel 346 VWEU toepassen. Beide landen gebruiken het artikel vooral om hun nationale defensie-industrieën te beschermen via directe gunningen. Sinds de Russische invasie van Oekraïne is het gebruik in beide landen toegenomen, waarbij Duitsland ook urgentie als rechtvaardiging lijkt op te voeren om artikel 346 in te roepen.

In aansluiting hierop is de juridische houdbaarheid van het gebruik van 346 VWEU op de verschillende gronden besproken. Juridisch zijn directe gunningen en offsetverplichtingen onder artikel 346 alleen toegestaan als zij strikt noodzakelijk en proportioneel zijn voor de bescherming van nationale veiligheid. Bij financieel sterke industrieën is dat moeilijker te rechtvaardigen. Vertrouwelijkheid is in principe wel toegestaan als het risico op schade aan de nationale veiligheid reëel is. In principe volstaat echter de speciale procedure onder de Richtlijn Aanbestedingen, welke in gevallen toelaat dat slechts drie producenten technische informatie verkrijgen over de aanbestedingen. Wanneer ook dit gevaren met zich meebrengt mag artikel 346 worden ingeroepen. Efficiëntie of snelheid geldt daarentegen niet als geldige reden voor afwijking van de Richtlijn Defensieaanbestedingen; daarvoor bestaan aparte versnellingsmechanismen binnen de Richtlijn Defensieaanbestedingen zelf die volstaan.

Vervolgens is besproken hoe het gebruik van artikel 346 VWEU beter kan worden afgestemd op het streven van Europese strategische autonomie. De uiteenlopende en vaak niet-transparante toepassing van dit artikel door lidstaten belemmert concurrentie en economische schaalvoordelen, en interoperabiliteit binnen de Europese defensiemarkt. Hoewel de Europese Commissie met voorstellen komt in het *ReArm Europe Plan/Readiness 2030*-plan evenals in een voorstel tot amendering van de Richtlijn Defensieaanbestedingen, volstaan deze niet. Daarom doe ik twee voorstellen. Ten eerste zou de Europese Commissie haar verouderde interpretatieve mededeling uit 2006 moeten actualiseren, zodat duidelijker wordt wanneer en onder welke voorwaarden artikel 346 rechtmatig kan worden ingeroepen. Dit zou rechtszekerheid bevorderen en misbruik van de uitzondering tegengaan. Dit kan gekoppeld worden aan het sterker toezien op het gebruik van Artikel 346 en het starten van inbreukprocedures. Ten tweede stel ik voor om een vertrouwelijke meldingsplicht in te voeren. Lidstaten zouden in dat geval de Commissie vooraf moeten informeren wanneer zij artikel 346 toepassen bij grote defensieopdrachten. Dit zou de transparantie vergroten, wederzijds vertrouwen versterken en bijdragen aan betere afstemming, zeker bij grensoverschrijdende projecten.

Geconcludeerd kan worden dat Nederland en Duitsland artikel 346 VWEU vaak ruim toepassen zonder coördinatie of transparantie, wat Europese strategische autonomie belemmert. Om dit te verbeteren worden twee voorstellen uitgewerkt.

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INTERVIEWS

Jorn Bleijs (Utrecht, 22 May 2024)

Jorn Bleijs is Head of the Projects Procurement Department at the Netherlands Ministry of Defence within the Materiel and IT Command. In this capacity, he oversees complex procurement projects that are critical to the Dutch armed forces.

Marc Greitens (videocall, 5 May 2025)

Marc Philip Greitens is a German lawyer and expert in public procurement law, with a particular focus on defence and security procurement. As a partner at Heuking in Hamburg, Marc offers legal services to national and international clients on complex procurement processes. Moreover, Greitens currently pursues a PhD at the Bucerius Law School and has contributed to academic discourse on procurement law. Additionally, he is a lecturer at the Helmut-Schmidt-University, the university of the German federal armed forces.

Roland Haag (email, 13 May 2025)

Roland Haag is Head of Economy and Law at the BDSV, where he oversees legal and economic issues affecting the German defence industry. He focuses on export controls, regulatory frameworks, and supply chain resilience.

Dr. Marc Pauka (videocall, 2 May 2025)

Dr. Marc Pauka is a German lawyer in the area of national and EU public procurement law. He holds the title of *Fachanwalt für Vergaberecht* (Specialist Lawyer for Public Procurement Law) and currently serves as head of the team ‘public procurement law’ at BWI GmbH, the German IT-system house of the German Armed Forces. He and his team of in-house lawyers provide strategic and operational advice in the area of public procurement law and public commercial law. Academically, he has received his doctorate from the University of Bonn with a thesis on international public law and contributed to academic discourse on procurement law, including publications in the *European Procurement & Public Private Partnership Law Review*.

Prof. Dr. Martin Trybus (videocall, 6 May 2025)

Prof. Martin Trybus is a leading expert in European defence procurement law. He is a Professor of European Law and Policy, and Director of the Institute of European Law at the University of Birmingham. His seminal work, *Buying Defence and Security in Europe: The EU Defence and Security Procurement Directive in Context*, provides a comprehensive analysis of Directive 2009/81/EC. Beyond academia, He also advises (inter)national organizations and gives training sessions to defence procurement professionals across EU Member States.

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PERSONAL CLOSING NOTE

I write this note with a heavy heart, concerned with the enduring scourge of armed conflict that shadows our world today. Wars, such as the ones on the Palestinian and Ukrainian people, show that violence, once unleashed, results in massive suffering and destruction. While this thesis factually and stoically reflects on the law of defence public procurement, war is inherently connected to lost lives, torn-apart families, and uprooted communities. It is a tragedy that, despite the progress of international law culminating in the worldwide ratification United Nations Charter, armed conflict persists at such a high scale.

At the same time, I acknowledge the necessity of rearmament for states seeking to protect their citizens in an increasingly unstable geopolitical landscape. National defence and deterrence also serve as a prevention mechanism against aggression. Yet this realization must not blind us to the sorrow that rearmament brings: the allocation of vast resources to instruments of death, and the inclination to use these instruments offensively abroad on other peoples in other continents.

Perhaps most distressing is the corrosion of the international norms. Principles such as the prohibition on the use of force and the obligation to settle disputes by peaceful means are actively eroded and are collapsing under geopolitical weight. Nevertheless, I remain hopeful that legal scholarship and democratic policymaking can help revive respect for the rule of law in international politics.

Floris Prins

ANNEX I: DUTCH INVOCATIONS OF ARTICLE 346 TFEU

<u>Project Name and Military Branch</u>	<u>Source</u> ³²⁸	<u>Use of Article 346 TFEU</u>	<u>Value</u>	<u>Time Path</u>
155mm Precision Guided Munition (PGM) voor de PzH2000	<i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2007-2008, 31200-X, nr. 104; <i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2014-2015, 27830, nr. 144; <i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2014-2015, 27830, nr. 146; <i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2022-2023, 27830, nr. 395; <i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2019-2020, 34225, nr. 25, p 1.	The project was awarded under competition with a procedure under Article 346 TFEU. No reason for invocation of Article 346 TFEU was given.	EUR 100.9 million	The earliest confirmed reference to the application of Article 346 TFEU: 13-03-2020 Delivery: 2026
ESSM Block 2: Verwerving en integratie (Navy)	<i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2017-2018, 27830, nr. 227, pp 4-5; <i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2021-2022, 27830, nr. 355, pp 4-6; <i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2023-2024, 27830, 430, pp 4-7.	The project comprises three subprojects. One of these subprojects, the integration of the missile system on the vessels, is directly awarded to Thales by Article 346 TFEU.	The whole project is valued at EUR 699 million. However, the procurement of the missile systems, which is not awarded under Article 346 TFEU, likely comprises the majority of the budget.	The earliest confirmed reference to the application of Article 346 TFEU: 09-05-2022 Delivery and integration in other equipment: 2027-2029.
Foxtrot	<i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2020-2021, 27830, nr. 316, 4-5; <i>Kamerstukken II</i>	The sensitive nature of the equipment means that there are essential	EUR 1 billion – 2.5 billion.	The earliest confirmed reference to the potential application of

³²⁸ Some of the sources in this Annex I are already mentioned in the thesis; Annex I lists all sources in the context of the tenders listed. Moreover, the following two sources were universally used for all the projects in Annex I: Ministry of Defence 2024 (2) (n 139); Ministry of Defence, 'Defensie Projectenoverzicht 2025' (Ministry of Defence 2025) <<https://www.defensie.nl/downloads/publicaties/2025/05/21/defensie-projectenoverzicht-2025>> accessed 27 June 2025.

	2023-2024, 27830, nr. 418.	interests of national security involved. Article 346 TFEU can be applied, for example for military radios and security keys for communication. However, the application has not been confirmed. Moreover, the Ministry of Economic Affairs is researching whether offsets can play a part in the project.		Article 346 TFEU: 05-12-2023 Delivery 2024-2034.
Multifunctionele ondersteuningsvaartuigen (Navy)	<i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2024-2025, 27830, nr. 446, pp 5-7.	Article 346 TFEU is applied to directly award the contract to Damen for the supply of vessels, and to directly award Israeli firm IAI with a contract to supply surface to air missile system. The ministry does state that there is only one suitable product available. Therefore, Article 346 TFEU is likely invoked because of the offsets that are involved.	EUR 250 million – 1 billion.	The earliest confirmed reference to the application of Article 346 TFEU: 09-10-2024 Delivery: 2026-2027

Annex I: Dutch Invocations of Article 346 TFEU

Onderzeeboten	<p><i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2019-2020, 34225, nr. 24, pp 3-5;</p> <p><i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2019-2020, 34225, nr. 25, p 31;</p> <p>‘Basisrapportage programma vervanging onderzeebootcapaciteit (BS202101057, 2021)’</p> <p><https://www.tweedekamer.nl/kamerstukken/detail?id=2021D20510&did=2021D20510> accessed 27 June 2025, pp 4, 6-7;</p> <p><i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2022-2023, 34225, nr. 42;</p> <p><i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2022-2023, 34225, nr. 44;</p> <p><i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2023-2024, 27830, nr. 423, p 7; <i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2023-2024, 34225, nr. 52, pp 2-4, 7-8.</p>	<p>The Netherlands invokes Article 346 TFEU to justify restricted tendering with four foreign shipyards. Two grounds are identified. First, secrecy: submarines are strategic assets, and disclosure of technical and operational details would compromise national security and the interests of the shipyards and their governments. Second, industrial participation: an Industrial Cooperation Agreement was entered into to strengthen the NLDTIB. About EUR 1 billion will be subcontracted by the Naval Group to the Dutch industry.</p>	EUR 5.6 billion.	<p>The earliest confirmed reference to the application of Article 346 TFEU: 18-12-2019</p> <p>The last submarine will be operational between 2034-2037.</p>
Verbeterd Operationeel Systeem Soldaat (VOSS)	<p><i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2007-2009, 31200-X, nr. 105;</p> <p><i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2009-2010, 32123-X, nr. 130;</p> <p><i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2011-2012,</p>	<p>The project was directly awarded under competition. Ten parties were contacted, after which four preferred bidders were selected.</p>	EUR 868.7 million	<p>The earliest confirmed reference to the application of Article 346 TFEU: 13-03-2020</p> <p>Delivery: Q1 2023-2024</p>

	33000-X, nr. 3, p 4; <i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2014-2015, 34000-X, nr. 98; <i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2019-2020, 34225, nr. 25, p 1.	No reason for invocation of Article 346 TFEU was given.		
Vervanging Close-in Weapon System (Navy)	<i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2017-2018, 27830, nr. 220, pp 2-3; <i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2020-2021 27830, nr. 329, pp 4-7; <i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2024-2024, 27830, nr. 453, pp 3-6.	The project comprises eight contracts, of which Thales is involved in five. The contracts with Thales are awarded under Article 346 TFEU. The other contracts are awarded under the Directive. The ministry explains that the direct award takes place to support the NLDTIB. ³²⁹	EUR 250 million – 1 billion.	The earliest confirmed reference to the application of Article 346 TFEU: 27-01-2021 Delivery and installation in other equipment: 2028-2032.
Vervanging M-fregatten (ASWF) (Navy)	<i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2017-2018, 27830, nr. 224, pp 3-4; <i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2019-2020, 27830, nr. 307, pp 2-8; <i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2022-2023, 27830, nr. 393, pp 4-8; <i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2023-2024, 27830, nr. 423, pp 3-10.	The Ministry procures 4 vessels, of which two are bought by Belgium. The Ministry concludes approximately 40 contracts for the project. The two largest contracts for the construction of the ship and the radar and fire control system are directly awarded to Damen and	EUR 2.0 billion.	The earliest confirmed reference to the application of Article 346 TFEU: 07-05-2018 Delivery: 2028-2031.

³²⁹ *Kamerstukken II* 2020-2021 27830, nr. 329, p 5.

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		Thales respectively. The other contracts may also have been awarded under Article 346 TFEU.		
Vervanging hulpvaartuigen (Navy)	<i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2019-2020, 27830, nr. 305, pp 3-4; <i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2021-2022, 27830, nr. 361, pp 4-6; <i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2023-2024, 27830, nr. 423, pp 5-6.	The Ministry will award the contract to build the vessels to a Dutch firm under Article 346 TFEU. It has not been disclosed which firm will be awarded the contract. The contract will include the design, construction, supply and maintenance of the support vessels.	EUR 250 million – 1 billion	The earliest confirmed reference to the application of Article 346 TFEU: 24-06-2022 Delivery: 2026-2030.
vervanging LC fregatten (Navy)	<i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2023-2024, 27830, nr. 423, p 4; <i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2023-2024, 27830, nr. 426, pp 3-5, 7-8.	The procurement is directly awarded to Damen and Thales, while also involving the broader defence industry. Damen will deliver the ship platform, and Thales NL will deliver the radar and fire control system Secondly, for the armament of the ship, which the Dutch industry cannot produce,	More than EUR 2.5 billion.	The earliest confirmed reference to the application of Article 346 TFEU: 20-01-2024 Four frigates in total. First frigate delivered in 2034, every other frigate one to one and a half year later. Given the time necessary to make the frigates operational, the last frigate will

		the Ministry will demand offsets in its contracts, which requires the use of Article 346 TFEU as well.		be operational around 2041.
Vervanging MRAD & SHORAD (Army)	<i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2021-2022, 27830, nr. 359, pp 2-3; <i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2022-2023, 27830, nr. 404, pp 4-6; <i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2024-2024, 27830, nr. 448, pp 4-6.	The project comprises six systems: The MRAD system, SHORAD system, IT systems, ammunition, simulation systems and radars. The exclusion ground of 2.16 of the Aanbestedingswet op defensie- en veiligheidsgebied is applied to a part of the procurement. The exclusion ground concerned is Article 13(a) of the Directive and this is in practice the codification of Article 346(1)(a) TFEU, coupled with the ability to take positive action. ³³⁰ Only the main contract for the MRAD system, SHORAD system and IT system is	The total project is estimated to cost EUR 2.6 billion.	The earliest confirmed reference to the application of Article 346 TFEU: 24-06-2022 Delivery: 2028-2030.

³³⁰ Directorate-General for Internal Market and Services 2010 (n 33), pp 4-5.

Annex I: Dutch Invocations of Article 346 TFEU

		awarded to KDA applying the exclusion ground. The exclusion allows for the direct award to KDA to produce, among others, the MRAD and SHORAD launch facilities, fire control systems, simulation equipment and logistic support. Offsets are also involved: KDA will involve the Dutch industry where possible. Among others, Thales Nederland and Aalberts Groep will be involved.		
Verwerving Amfibische Transport-schepen	<i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2023-2024, 27830, nr. 427, 3-4, 6-7.	Direct award to Damen. The Dutch maritime industry will be closely engaged.	EUR 1 billion – 2.5 billion.	The earliest confirmed reference to the application of Article 346 TFEU: 12-03-2024 Delivery between 2032-2037. The first ship is delivered around 2032, after which one of the five ships is delivered every year.
Verwerving Combat Support Ship (Navy)	<i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2017-2018, 27830, nr. 212,	Direct award to Damen. Damen was also the	EUR 458 million.	The earliest confirmed reference to the

	pp 2-3; <i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2019-2020, 27830, nr. 300, pp 2-5.	manufacturer of the Joint Support Ship, which design is similar to the combat support ship. There is also an industrial cooperation agreement with Damen.		application of Article 346 TFEU: 07-05- 2018 Delivery: 2024. Operational: 2025
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ANNEX II: GERMAN INVOCATIONS OF ARTICLE 346 TFEU

<u>Project Name and Military Branch</u>	<u>Source</u>	<u>Use of Article 346 TFEU</u>	<u>Value</u>	<u>Time Path</u>
62 H145M Helicopters (Air force)	Sebastian Sprenger, 'Germany spends \$2.3 billion on Airbus light attack helicopters' (<i>Defense News</i> , 2023) https://www.defensenews.com/global/europe/2023/12/14/germany-spends-23-billion-on-airbus-light-attack-helicopters/ accessed 27 June 2025; Bundestag, 'Stenografischer Bericht: 81. Sitzung' (Plenarprotokoll 20/81, 25 January 2023) < https://dserver.bundestag.de/btp/20/20081.pdf > accessed 27 June 2025, p 9719; Noah Heinemann, 'What Are the Main Drivers of Member States' Defence Procurement Practices? The	The contract was directly awarded to airbus, which produces the helicopters in Germany. The source notes that the invocation took place because of urgency reasons.	The contract was valued at approximately USD 2,3 billion.	The earliest confirmed reference to the application of Article 346 TFEU: 25-05-2023 Deliveries began in 2024.

	<p>German Case' (ARES Group, 2025) https://www.iris-france.org/en/what-are-the-main-drivers-of-member-states-defence-procurement-practices-the-german-case/ accessed 27 June 2025, pp 3-4; Airbus, 'Airbus in Germany' (Airbus) https://www.airbus.com/en/about-us/our-worldwide-presence/airbus-in-europe/airbus-in-germany accessed 27 June 2025.</p>			
155 mm ammunition	<p>Bundestag, 'Antwort der Bundesregierung auf die Kleine Anfrage der Fraktion der CDU/CSU: Munition in der Bundeswehr: Aktueller Sachstand, Bedarfe und Planungen' (Drucksache 20/4509, 14 November 2022) https://dserver.bundestag.de/btd/20/045/2004509.pdf accessed</p>	<p>The contract was directly awarded. The parliamentarian asks whether an accelerated award was made or whether Article 346 TFEU was applied, thereby implying urgency was important in this purchase.</p>	<p>Up to EUR 8.5 billion.</p>	<p>The earliest confirmed reference to the application of Article 346 TFEU: 14-11-2022 Deliveries begin in 2025.</p>

Annex II: German Invocations of Article 346 TFEU

	<p>27 June 2025, p 12; Rheinmetall AG, ‘Largest order in company history: Rheinmetall receives framework contract for 155mm artillery ammunition for the Bundeswehr with a total gross value of up to €8.5 billion’ (<i>Rheinmetall</i>, 20 June 2024) <https://www.rheinmetall.com/en/media/news-watch/news/2024/06/2024-06-20-rheinmetall-receives-framework-contract-for-155mm-ammunition> accessed 27 June 2025.</p>			
Caracal Air Assault Vehicles	<p><i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2022-2023, 27830, nr. 409; <i>Kamerstukken II</i> 2022-2023, 27830, nr. 407; Rojoef Manuel, ‘Rheinmetall Clinches \$2B Caracal Air Assault Vehicle Contract for Germany, Netherlands’ (<i>The Defense Post</i>, 12 July 2023) <https://thedefensepost.com/2023</p>	Unknown	USD 1,9 billion.	<p>The earliest confirmed reference to the application of Article 346 TFEU: 06-07-2023</p> <p>Deliveries start in 2025.</p>

	/07/12/germany-netherlands-caracal-contract-rheinmetall/> accessed 27 June 2025.			
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